

“Comparison of Inhalational Drugs Formoterol + Glycopyrronium (LABA-LAMA) vs. Formoterol + Budesonide (LABA-ICS) and outcomes in cases of C.O.P.D.-Randomized Control Trial”

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In partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of

DOCTOR OF MEDICINE

IN

RESPIRATORY MEDICINE

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

COPD : Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

FM : Formoterol

BD : Budesonide

GP : Glycopyrronium

RCT : Randomized Control Trial

LABA : Long acting beta agonist

LAMA : Long acting muscarinic agonist

ICS : Inhaled Corticosteroid

VEGF : Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor

ATP : Adenosine Triphosphate

cAMP : Cyclic Adenosine Monophosphate

Vd : Volume Distributed

M2 : Muscarinic Receptor 2

M3 : Muscarinic Receptor 3

B : Beta Receptor

UK : United Kingdom

CAD : Coronary Artery Disease

% : Percentage

FEV1 : Forced expiratory volume in 1st second

MMRC : Modified medical research council

CAT : COPD Assessment test

CCQ : Clinical COPD questionnaire

CD 8+ : Cluster differentiated cells

EELV : End expiratory lung volume

MMP 12 : Matrix metalloproteinases 12

FVC : Forced vital capacity

ROS : Reactive oxygen species

GOLD : Global initiative for obstructive lung diseases

AECOPD : Acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

MMEF : Maximum mid expiratory flow

MVV : Maximal voluntary ventilation

RV : Residual volume

TLC : Total lung capacity

DLCO : Diffusing capacity of the lungs for carbon monoxide

S COPD : Stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

PaCO₂ : Partial pressure of carbon di oxide

PaO₂ : Partial pressure of oxygen

HsCRP : Highly sensitive C-Reactive protein

HIV : Human Immunodeficiency Virus

CRP : C-Reactive protein

Cr : Creatinine

SI : Sarcopenic index

HRQOL : Health related quality of life

6MWT : 6 minute walk test

BMI : Body mass index

BODE: (Body mass index, Airflow obstruction , Dyspnea ,and exercise opacity)

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND:

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), which is now the fourth leading cause of mortality worldwide but is anticipated to become the third most common reason by 2020, is a significant public health issue that is both curable and preventable. In 2012, COPD claimed the lives of more than 3 million individuals, or 6% of all fatalities worldwide. A significant public health issue that is both preventable and curable is COPD.

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a chronic inflammatory disease with high mortality and morbidity. In this study we are comparing two combinations LABA -ICS (Formoterol – Budesonide) and LABA – LAMA (Formoterol- Glycopyrronium). Inhalers are compared based on spirometry, Exercise tests such as six-minute walk test and BODE Index. Patients were assessed on by MMRC Scale, CAT and CCQ questionnaires, Adverse effects were taken in account on follow up.

The newer GOLD 2022 guidelines have no specific recommendation regarding the choice of drugs and suggest using LABA+ICS or LABA+LAMA or LAMA drugs for treating COPD. Hence, the efficacy of the above combinations for treatment of COPD. is to be determined. Studies suggest LABA+ICS is better than LABA+LAMA, whereas others suggest otherwise, and other studies suggest similar efficacy between these inhalational drugs. They are studies which also suggest different side effects of these combinations. Hence there is a need to evaluate a better combination in the treatment of COPD patients.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To determine changes in Spirometry in changes, 6-minute walk test in Formoterol + Budesonide vs. Formoterol + Glycopyrronium in COPD patients
- To compare side effects and changes in quality of life (Q.O.L.) in Formoterol + Budesonide vs. Formoterol + Glycopyrronium in COPD patients

MATERIALS AND METHODS

COPD patients visiting the Department of Respiratory Medicine, B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura will be included in this study. It is a randomized Control Trial done over a duration of two years⁷⁰ COPD. Patients (35 patients in FM-GP, 35 patients in FM-BD) were evaluated on basis of spirometry, questionnaires and exercise tests and re-evaluated 3 months later

RESULTS

In this study, majority of the patients were of age group 60-69 age group and mean BMI of 21.5, with male dominance Smoking index of more than 20 was predominant in patients with severe and very severe COPD. Biomass exposure to more than 20 years was predominantly more in patients with severe grades of COPD. Out of 70 patients 4 patients didn't appear for follow up and one patient in FM-BD group succumbed to death 2 months after initiating FM-BD inhaler.

Spirometry data were analyzed in both groups Post bronchodilator FEV1 % predicted showed significant improvement in FM-GP group (p -0.01) when compared to FM-BD group and the mean change when compared was insignificant. (p-0.103) Post bronchodilator FVC % showed no improvement in individual groups and in mean change on second visit. Change in FEV1 was significantly more in FM-BD group when compared to FM-GP group and mean change in Post bronchodilator change in FEV1 was significantly (p -0.008) more in FM-BD

group when compared to FM-GP group.

Both treatments were effective in improving MMRC scores, FM-GP therapy showed a statistically significant($p=0.019$) advantage over FM-BD therapy in reducing dyspnea symptoms in COPD patients after two visits.

6MWT and BODE INDEX had increased improvement on follow up in both the groups, mean change in 6MWT was insignificant($p=0.4$) when both the groups were compared, mean BODE index significantly($p=0.04$) reduced in FM-GP group when compared to FM-BD group.

The FM-BD group shows a higher incidence of adverse effects, exacerbations, hospitalizations (both ward and ICU admissions), and death within 3 months of the first visit compared to the FM-GP group.

On the basis of questionnaires when both the groups were compared, individual improvement was observed in both groups respectively. The CAT and CCQ scores mean change of both groups when compared showed no significant difference between them respectively ($p=0.72$, $p=0.93$).

CONCLUSION

FM-GP group has shown significantly more improvement in MMR, BODE Index and reduced adverse effects and rate of exacerbations when compared with FM-BD group. Mean Change in post bronchodilator change in FEV1 was significantly more in FM-BD group when compared with FM-GP group.

KEYWORDS: COPD, FORMOTEROL, GLYCOPYRRONIUM, BUDESONIDE, MMRC, CAT, CCQ, BODE

INTRODUCTION

A serious public health problem that can be prevented and treated is chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), which is currently the fourth major cause of death worldwide but is predicted to be the third leading cause by 2020.⁽¹⁾

COPD is defined by enduring respiratory symptoms and airflow restrictions that are brought on by anomalies in the airways and/or alveoli, which are typically brought on by prolonged exposure to noxious particles or gases. Not only can acute exacerbations of COPD enhance airway inflammation, but also systemic inflammation. The imbalance between protease and anti-protease is a component of the pathophysiology.⁽²⁾

The severity of COPD is usually assessed based on a single parameter – forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV 1). The patients with COPD have systemic manifestations that are not reflected by FEV1.⁽²⁾

A multidimensional grading system that assessed the respiratory and systemic expressions of COPD was designed to predict outcomes in these patients.

The four factors that predicted the severity most were the body-mass index (B), the degree of airflow obstruction (O) and dyspnea (D), and exercise capacity (E), measured by the six-minute-walk test.

Long-acting bronchodilator medications, which include long-acting b2- agonists (LABA) and long-acting muscarinic antagonists (LAMA), have become central maintenance therapy to the management of COPD, with inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) added with increasing severity.

Adverse events associated with inhaled glucocorticoids include pneumonia, bone fractures, and cataracts, for which the magnitude of risk may depends on the duration, dose, and type of inhaled glucocorticoid used for the treatment.

The newer GOLD 2022 guidelines have no specific recommendation regarding the choice of drugs and suggest using LABA+ICS or LABA+LAMA or LAMA drugs for treating COPD. Hence, the efficacy of the above combinations for treatment of COPD. is to be determined. Studies suggest LABA+ICS is better than LABA+LAMA, whereas others suggest otherwise, and other studies suggest similar efficacy between these inhalational drugs.^(3,4)

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

PRIMARY OBJECTIVES

- To determine changes in Spirometry in (LABA+LAMA) Formoterol + Glycopyrronium vs. (LABA+ICS) Formoterol + Budesonide patients.
- To determine changes in 6-minute walk test in (LABA+LAMA) Formoterol + Glycopyrronium vs. (LABA+ICS) Formoterol + Budesonide patients.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

- To compare side effects of (LABA+LAMA) Formoterol + Glycopyrronium vs. (LABA+ICS) Formoterol + Budesonide
- To compare changes in quality of life (Q.O.L.) in (LABA +LAMA) Formoterol + Glycopyrronium vs. (LABA +ICS) Formoterol +Budesonide

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HISTORY

Since the period of Laennec, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease has been extensively investigated. The relationship between the Disease and smoking was not made until the beginning of the first half of the 20th century. ⁽⁷⁾

By OPIE, et al. in 1905, the concept of an enzyme imbalance and the presence of antienzymes as a potential cause of emphysema was first documented. ⁽⁸⁾

There were also other more emphysema research studies. Emphysema most frequently impacted the heart, according to a study done in 1934 by Kountz and Alexander.

A vascular atrophy model of the illness was also put up by Liebow et al. in the 1950s.

Proteinase and anti-proteinase hypothesis in emphysema was developed in 1960 as a result of Gross and his co-workers' discovery that patients with emphysema had a 1 antitrypsin deficit.

In its publication, the Medical Research Council introduced the phrase "chronic bronchitis" for the first time in 1956 to describe an illness characterized by a persistent cough and expectoration when other causes, such as pulmonary tuberculosis and bronchiectasis, were ruled out. ⁽⁹⁾

In the year, Higgins discovered a connection between smoking and persistent coughing and sputum production in 1959. ⁽¹⁰⁾

Owen and Campell discovered the pathological abnormalities brought on by smoking in 18 airways in the late 1960. ⁽¹¹⁾

Dr. William Briscoe is thought to be the first person to use the term "chronic obstructive pulmonary disorder" at the 9th Aspen Emphysema Conference in June of 1965.

In 1971, 108 people with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease were investigated by Boushy

SF et al. The pulmonary function test and hemodynamic data were linked with the ECG. (12)

A series of publications on chronic obstructive pulmonary disease prognostic factors were published in 1973 by Bougly and colleagues mainly includes Lung function test prognostic values in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Diseases and pulmonary disease.

Due to the long-term nature of this disease's course, it puts a significant strain on the resources of the healthcare system. Since COPD is a condition that may be prevented, it is extremely important for public health.

PREVALANCE:

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), which is now the fourth leading cause of mortality worldwide but is anticipated to become the third most common reason by 2020 (1), is a significant public health issue that is both curable and preventable.

In 2012, COPD claimed the lives of more than 3 million individuals (1), or 6% of all fatalities worldwide. A significant public health issue that is both preventable and curable is COPD. It affects middle-aged and older people, and people under the age of 35 are less likely to contract it.

Due to their higher smoking prevalence than women, men are the most frequently impacted. Due to an increase in environmental trigger factors throughout the winter, COPD exacerbations are more common.

Previous research from other regions of the country claimed that among people over 40, the prevalence of chronic bronchitis was as high as 16% in North India (13) than in South India because of the climatic fluctuations there.

Another study by Bhattacharya et al. (14) revealed that 57 per 1000 people in a rural population had chronic bronchitis by the age of 30 or older. The incidence of the disease increased in direct proportion to age and the number of pack-years of smoking.

PREVALENCE IN WESTERN COUNTRIES:

Around 16 million people in the USA are thought to have COPD, of which 14 million have chronic bronchitis and another 2 million have emphysema. The male-to-female ratio varies between 4 and 6% and 1 and 3%. With almost 1 lakh deaths each year, it is the third most common cause of mortality in the USA.

Prospective research conducted in the UK including 40,000 medical professionals revealed that chronic bronchitis was higher in smokers and proportional to pack years.

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)

The hallmarks of COPD are persistent respiratory symptoms and airflow restriction brought on by abnormalities in the airways or alveoli, which are typically brought on by prolonged exposure to harmful particles or gases.

The majority of patients exhibit pathologic airway alterations consistent with chronic bronchitis in addition to the air space degradation associated with emphysema. Subsets of the COPD population may, however, vary in their response to therapeutic intervention and natural history. For two or more years, the qualifying criterion of chronic bronchitis is a daily cough and sputum for three months.

Common, treatable, and preventable lung disease that is primarily brought on by a significant cumulative long-term exposure to harmful particles or gases (like smoking cigarettes), along with other factors like genetics, hyperresponsiveness of the airways, and abnormal lung development. The end result is airflow limitations caused by chronic airway inflammation and/or parenchymal destruction (emphysema) ⁽¹⁵⁾

The Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) does not include the terms "emphysema" or "chronic bronchitis" in its definition of COPD.

i. Excessive sputum production and coughing for at least three months every year for two

consecutive years is known as chronic bronchitis.

ii. The pathological name for the deterioration of the lung's gas-exchanging surfaces is emphysema (alveoli).

Acute worsening of respiratory symptoms necessitating additional therapy is referred to as a COPD exacerbation. (15)

Epidemiology ⁽¹⁵⁾

90% of COPD deaths reported to occur in low- and middle-income countries prevalence increases with age, but unclear if healthy ageing leads to COPD or if age reflects sum of cumulative exposures throughout life.

Graph 1: Decline in lung function with age⁽¹⁾

An estimated 175 million adults worldwide are thought to have COPD, an adult disease that typically manifests in the sixth or later decade of life. COPD is the third most common cause of death in the world, with an estimated 3.2 million deaths each year. ⁽¹⁶⁾ Given the time lag between starting to smoke and the manifestation of clinical illness, the frequency of cigarette smoking worldwide, and the average population age predict that the number of cases will

continue to climb. The projected yearly cost of COPD in the United States is \$50 billion, of which \$30 billion is spent on direct medical expenses and \$20 billion on indirect expenses. The idea that smoking cigarette is the main risk factor for the onset of COPD is supported by epidemiologic data. The "dose" of smoking, expressed in pack-years is inversely correlated with FEV 1 at the population level.

Lower peak lung function in adulthood is caused by factors that prevent full lung development, such as childhood respiratory illnesses; subsequent decrease, whether or not it is accelerated, can lead to the development of COPD.

The primary cause of COPD is unquestionably cigarette smoking, but other exposures are also linked, particularly when biomass fuels are burned in poorly ventilated areas where they are used for heating and cooking. Less is known about the function of environmental air pollution.

People who are exposed to workplace dust in mines, grain-handling facilities, and cotton mills may also have coughing, sputum, and a permanent loss of lung function. Research showing that higher pollution levels are temporally related to higher mortality in individuals with existing COPD. It is unknown if previous respiratory infections have any lasting consequences on adult lung function.

Risk factors

Factors associated with COPD development and progression.

- Tobacco smoke (active smoking or passive environmental exposure)
- other particle exposures such as
 - outdoor air pollution such as from urban environments
 - Indoor air pollution such as animal dung, crop residues, burning wood, or coal.
 - occupational exposures including organic and inorganic dusts, chemical

agents, and fumes.

- genetic factors and family history of COPD
- demographic factors
 - older age
 - male sex
 - low socioeconomic status
- Respiratory features including
 - suboptimal lung development during gestation or childhood (including leading to reduced maximal attained lung function)
 - asthma and airway hyperreactivity
 - infections such as
 - history of severe childhood respiratory infection
 - *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infection
 - Tuberculosis
 - chronic bronchitis
 - HIV

Associated Conditions ⁽¹⁵⁾

- COPD frequently co-occurs with comorbidities (due to causal or exacerbating relationship and/or shared risk factors) which may affect prognosis and management strategies.
 - shared symptoms and/or signs between COPD and multiple frequent comorbidities necessitate careful evaluation and consideration.
 - COPD may occur as part of multi-morbidity (≥ 2 chronic conditions)
- significant comorbidities include ⁽¹⁵⁾

- cardiovascular diseases, including
- hypertension
- CAD
- atrial fibrillation
- peripheral vascular disease
- heart failure with reduced ejection fraction or heart failure with preserved ejection fraction
- increased subclinical cardiovascular disease assessed by surrogate markers (carotid intima-media thickness and arterial stiffness measured by pulse wave velocity)
- lung cancer ⁽¹⁵⁾
 - risk factors for lung cancer in patients with COPD include
 - age > 55 years
 - smoking history > 30 pack years
 - emphysema on computed tomography scan
 - airflow limitation on forced expiratory volume in 1 second/forced vital capacity < 0.7
 - body mass index < 25 kg/m²
 - family history of lung cancer

Etiology and pathogenesis:

Causes:⁽¹⁵⁾

- Persistent airway inflammation and/or parenchymal destruction brought on by prolonged cumulative exposure to noxious particles or gases (such as cigarette smoking) and other factors like heredity and faulty lung development (emphysema)

- People who never smoked can also get COPD, while it is uncertain what causes the inflammatory response in these circumstances.

Pathogenesis ⁽¹⁵⁾:

According to data, the pulmonary vasculature, lung parenchyma, and airways all play significant roles in COPD patients. The relative relevance of these processes differs between patients, which affects how the disease manifests and how it responds to treatment.

The protease-antiprotease theory is the most widely recognized idea for how emphysema develops. According to this idea, emphysema happens when there is an excess of elastolytic protease activity compared to antiprotease levels. This theory's foundation is the finding that those who are lacking in α_1 -antiprotease have a higher likelihood of acquiring emphysema. α_1 -Antiprotease is a significant inhibitor of neutrophil elastase and a member of the serpin (serine protease inhibitor) superfamily. Emphysema can result from the degradation of elastin by proteases. Emphysema can also be brought on by macrophage elastases in addition to neutrophil elastase.

Smoking cigarettes cause an influx of inflammatory cells, such as neutrophils and macrophages, into the lung. In terms of quantity, macrophages make up the majority of this reaction. The theories that vascular processes and apoptosis may play a role in the emergence of emphysema are also supported by experimental findings. Smokers frequently experience small airway irritation and the presence of pigmented macrophages.

Neutrophils and CD8⁺ lymphocytes are also crucial elements of the inflammatory response. Eosinophils are a very minor part of the inflammatory response in COPD, in contrast to many asthma patients, but a subset of COPD patients exhibit sputum and peripheral eosinophilia. Reactive oxygen species and oxidative stress may play a role in the signaling that supports this inflammatory response.

The inflammatory response in the lung is still present in COPD patients even after they stop smoking. This finding offers a plausible explanation for the clinical observation of the disease's ongoing development despite smoking cessation, along with data on microbiome changes and evidence of autoimmunity in people with COPD.

Smoking results in intimal thickening, smooth muscle proliferation, a reduction in VEGF production, and endothelial cell death in septal arteries in emphysema patients' pulmonary vasculature. Emphysema can be created by manipulating VEGF expression in animal models, which implies that pulmonary vascular alterations may be the main cause of COPD in some people. Chronic hypoxemia also causes pulmonary vascular constriction, which eventually results in pulmonary hypertension.

In chronic bronchitis, symptoms of cough and excessive sputum production are all correlated with hypertrophied bronchial mucous glands, an increased epithelial goblet cell population, and increased airway mucin concentration, but not with airflow restriction.

FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR DISEASE DEVELOPMENT AND PROGRESSION:

GENETIC FACTORS^(17,18,19)

A significant hereditary deficiency of alpha-1 antitrypsin (AATD), a key circulating inhibitor of serine proteases, is the genetic risk factor linked to COPD.

This AATD deficit shows how environmental exposures and genetics interact to predispose an individual to COPD, although only affecting a small portion of the global population.

About 0.12% of COPD patients had AATD PiZZ genotypes, according to a systematic

assessment of 20 studies in the European population. The incidence of these genotypes ranged from 1 in 408 in the northern part of Europe to 1 in 1,274 in the eastern part. Smokers and siblings of patients with severe COPD disease also showed a high familial risk of airflow limitation, indicating that genetics and environmental factors may work together to generate this susceptibility. Single genes have also been linked to the deterioration of lung function and the risk of COPD. Examples of these genes are glutathione S-transferase and the gene encoding matrix metallo-proteinase 12 (MMP-12).

AGE AND SEX:

Growing older is frequently cited as a significant risk factor for COPD. The aging process of the lung parenchyma and airways is similar to the structural alterations linked to COPD. Clinically significant variations in immunological pathways and airway damage patterns can be observed depending on gender. Previous research has indicated that men are more likely than women to have COPD, both in terms of prevalence and mortality. However, data from developed nations has since shown that COPD prevalence is nearly equal in both genders, likely due to changing tobacco smoking patterns. Though contentious, recent research indicates that women may be more vulnerable than men to the negative consequences of smoking, which could result in a more severe illness for the same amount of time.

LUNG GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT:

Lung growth is influenced by processes that take place during pregnancy, after delivery, and during infancy and adolescence. A person's chance of having COPD can be raised by any circumstance that may have an impact on lung growth throughout pregnancy and youth. Early-life variables referred to as "childhood disadvantage factors" are found to be just as significant in predicting lung function later in life as heavy smoking.

EXPOSURE TO PARTICLES^(20,21)

One of the main risk factors for COPD is thought to be cigarette smoking. Smokers experience a higher annual rate of decline in FEV1, a higher prevalence of respiratory symptoms, anomalies in lung function, and a higher death rate when compared to non-smokers.

Additional tobacco products, like 1. Pipe 2. Cigar 3. Water pipe 4. Another risk factor for COPD is marijuana use.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY:

COPD is indicated by obstruction of the expiratory airflow. Anatomically, this flow limitation is located in the small airways (less than 2 mm). A few of the mechanisms that can cause obstruction include constriction of the smooth muscles of the airways, inflammation of the small airways, wall thickening and scarring, loss of the small airways due to parenchymal destruction, and dynamic airway collapse due to the loss of parenchymal tethering secondary to the parenchymal destruction that is typical of emphysema.

In the context of parenchymal injury, a contemporaneous alteration might be a reduced driving power as a result of a loss of elastic rebound. The extended expiratory duration brought on by this airflow limitation may be seen as a definite "coving" of the flow rates with time on a spirogram the part of the flow volume loop that is expiratory. When the expiratory time is shortened prior to the beginning of the succeeding inspiration due to an elevated respiratory rate, only a portion of the previous tidal volume is expelled. In a situation known as dynamic hyperinflation, the end-expiratory lung volume (EELV) increases to the point where the expiratory flow rates are high enough to completely expel the preceding tidal volume.

Independent of hypoxemia, an increase in EELV might cause a feeling of dyspnea.

Emphysema, in its purest form, causes dynamic expiratory airway collapse as a result of the loss of tethering, the destruction of parenchymal tissue, the loss of tiny airways, and the loss of the alveolar gas exchange surface.

In contrast, chronic bronchitis is characterized by mucous gland enlargement and hypersecretion, increased airway responsiveness with subsequent dynamic smooth muscle constriction, and airway inflammation. Airflow obstruction and a persistent, productive cough that produces sputum are the results of this.

GENETICS:

Alpha One-antitrypsin deficiency is the most prevalent monogenic characteristic linked to COPD. The serine protease inhibitor that the liver produces and secretes, 4 alpha b-1-antitrypsin, is encoded by the SERPINA1 gene. A functional protein cannot be secreted as a result of the most frequent mutations linked to deficiency, which cause polymerization of 1 -antitrypsin in the liver.

Approximately 15% of normal circulating levels of alpha 1-antitrypsin are related with an increased risk of emphysema, bronchiectasis, and liver illness in some people.

The likelihood that these mutations induce clinically significant organ damage is probably influenced by other variables, particularly smoking, as fewer people than predicted are identified with COPD and 1 -antitrypsin deficiency. It is debatable if people who are heterozygous for a mutant allele have a higher chance of developing lung disease.

Emphysema or airflow restriction are two other hereditary disorders.

Cutis laxa (elastin, fibulin 4 and fibulin 5), Ehlers-Danlos syndrome, and Marfan syndrome are among the conditions caused by these genes. The finding that a minority of smokers acquire COPD and that there is family clustering of COPD cases have given rise to the theory that genetic variables account for the varied responses to cigarette smoke. MMP-12 and

Serpin E2 are two of the genes that have been linked, however these results have been contradictory. Current longitudinal research might perhaps offer greater proof of genetic influences on COPD.

CLINICAL FEATURES:

Persistent and Progressive Breathlessness is the sign of COPD (1). Maximum effort is frequently not constrained by ventilatory capacity; therefore, people might have substantial COPD before experiencing symptoms. Patients frequently experience symptoms for months or years before a COPD diagnosis is obtained due to the illness's sluggish course and the fact that other conditions including heart disease, obesity, and deconditioning can also cause dyspnea when exerted,²⁴

When a patient experiences an exacerbation, which is marked by increased dyspnea, coughing, and sputum production and may or may not be accompanied by fever and other constitutional symptoms suggestive of infection, the condition is commonly diagnosed as COPD. When these symptoms first appear, the patient may decide to consult a doctor, at which point the history may reveal exposures that increase the risk of COPD and prior exercise-induced dyspnea (usually persistent cigarette smoking). In a minority of persons, recurrent exacerbations play a crucial role in the course of COPD.

COPD with chronic bronchitis, by definition, has a persistent cough and phlegm. Patients with chronic bronchitis may experience hemoptysis, especially during an exacerbation. Clubbing is not a sign of COPD, therefore if you have it, you should get checked out for other diseases, such lung cancer or pulmonary fibrosis.²⁵

Hypoxemia or hypercarbia may occur in patients with more severe illness. Cyanosis can result from hypoxemia, which is often detected by pulse oximetry. An arterial blood gas test is necessary to confirm hypercarbia, which may be indicated by a raised serum bicarbonate

level.

Systemic symptoms of COPD might potentially include arrhythmias like atrial fibrillation.

Emphysema patients lose body mass and may become sarcopenic. An important restriction in activity may cause pulmonary hypertension to develop. COPD and depression frequently co-occur.

The diagnosis may be affected by a history of smoking, other inhalational exposures, preterm delivery or repeated lung infections in infancy, a cough (chronicity, frequency), and sputum production. The degree to which dyspnea restricts activity should be emphasised in particular since patients may gradually reduce activity over time to avoid the painful sensation of being out of breath and may not report having dyspnea when engaging in normal daily activities.

Patients should be questioned about coexisting conditions and any lung disease in their families.

A large anteroposterior thoracic dimension (barrel chest), the use of the arms to stabilise the shoulder girdle to enable the use of accessory muscles of respiration (tripod position), a history of less dyspnea when pushing a cart than when walking, and, in severe cases, retraction of the lower rib cage with inspiration due to the altered biomechanics of flattened diaphragms are all possible effects of chronic hyperinflation associated (Hoover sign).

Abdominal wall motion that contradicts itself with inspiration is a sign of fatigued respiratory muscles. Chest percussion may demonstrate elevated resonance. In patients with emphysema as their primary diagnosis, auscultation may indicate diminished breath sounds; asymmetry increases the risk of pneumothorax. When pushed to exhale, patients with airway illness may wheeze and have rhonchi.

The shape of the chest wall and the right heart's function are primarily implicated in cardiac abnormalities in COPD. A decrease in heart sounds might result from increased retrosternal

airspace. Elevated jugular venous pressure, a louder-than-normal pulmonic valve closure sound (P2), a right ventricular heave, hepatic congestion, and peripheral edema all enhance the risk of pulmonary hypertension (cor pulmonale). Given that smoking is a risk factor for lung cancer and that persons with COPD have an approximately 2-fold greater risk of acquiring lung cancer than smokers without COPD, hemoptysis should prompt a check to see whether the patient has lung cancer. Patients with emphysema as their predominant COPD symptom may have weight loss and sarcopenia, as revealed by a physical exam.

Assess severity of symptoms; useful tools include ⁽¹⁵⁾

- The modified Medical Research Council (mMRC) questionnaire uses a 4-point rating system to assess breathlessness, with 0 representing breathlessness during vigorous exercise and 4 representing being too out of breath to leave the house or to change into or out of clothing.
- The eight-item COPD Assessment Test (CAT) is a tool that can be used to assess a person's quality of life in relation to their health and condition.
- A patient's spirometric categorization, exacerbation risk, and/or symptom evaluation are combined to determine the impact of COPD on that particular patient. The "ABCD" assessment tool of the 2011 GOLD update marked a significant improvement over the simple spirometric grading system of previous versions of GOLD because it included patient-reported outcomes and emphasised the importance of exacerbation prevention in the management of COPD.
- To start, the ABCD evaluation method did not outperform spirometric grades in predicting death or other crucial health outcomes in COPD1. Additionally, results for group "D" were influenced by either exacerbation history or lung function, which led

to misunderstanding. A modification of the ABCD evaluation instrument is suggested that isolates spirometric grades from the "ABCD" categories in order to solve these and other issues (while retaining consistency and simplicity for the practical clinician). The ABCD categories for certain therapy suggestions are generated only from the symptoms and exacerbation history of the patient. Spirometry continues to be essential for the diagnosis, prognosis, and evaluation of other significant treatment options. It should be used in conjunction with patient symptoms and a history of mild and severe exacerbations. This novel method of assessment is demonstrated in the figure 1.

- While the letter (groups A to D) gives information regarding symptom load and exacerbation risk, which can be used to guide therapy, the number provides information regarding the degree of airflow limitation (spirometric grade 1 to 4). When predicting significant clinical outcomes like hospitalizations and mortality, or when it comes to recommending non-pharmacological treatments like lung volume reduction or lung transplantation, FEV1 is a crucial metric at the population level.

It is crucial to remember that FEV1 loses accuracy at the patient level and cannot be utilized in isolation to evaluate every available treatment option. Furthermore, the ability to assess patients based on symptoms and exacerbation history, independent of the spirometric value, permits clinicians to initiate a treatment plan based solely on the revised ABCD scheme in certain situations, such as during hospitalization or an urgent presentation to the clinic or emergency room. This assessment technique emphasizes the significance of patient symptoms and exacerbation risks in directing therapy in COPD and acknowledges the limitations of FEV1 in determining treatment decisions for tailored patient care. The differentiation between airflow limitation and clinical parameters

facilitates the evaluation and ranking process. This makes it possible to provide more accurate therapy recommendations depending on the variables that are influencing the patient's symptoms at any particular moment.

Fig:1 REFINED ABCD ASSESSMENT TOOL (1)

ACUTE EXACERBATION OF COPD:

An increase in dyspnea beyond the patient's typical level, a coughing fit, or an increase and modification in the nature of mucus production are all considered signs of an acute exacerbation of COPD. Roughly 60% of the direct medical expenses associated with COPD are attributable to acute exacerbations, which have an independent negative impact on quality of life and have a short-term death rate of about 10%.

The most prevalent mechanism for an exacerbation, regardless of the initial stimulus, is an inflammatory response that comprises airway inflammation, mucus hypersecretion, and airway smooth muscle constriction, which combined produce in the classic triad of dyspnea, cough, and sputum. It is possible to find viral or bacterial infections in 75–80% of COPD

acute exacerbations.

Rhinovirus, influenza, parainfluenza, respiratory syncytial virus, coronaviruses, and adenovirus are the viruses that are most commonly implicated. The bacterial species that have been linked to exacerbations in a number of individuals with chronic bronchitis include *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, and, to a lesser extent, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Other environmental exposures most certainly have a role as well, especially in the 20 to 25 percent of cases when no pathogen or viral exposure was found. For instance, people with COPD who visit the emergency room more frequently for respiratory symptoms do so when ambient air pollution is higher.

Clinical Manifestations and Diagnosis:

The symptoms of acute exacerbations of COPD are typically comparable to those of acute bronchitis because they are frequently accompanied by fever or happen after contact with ill people. Questions concerning the patient's recent history of exacerbations, concomitant conditions including heart disease, previous viral exposures, baseline functional state, past treatment responses (if any), and the presence of somnolence or disorientation that might indicate hypercarbia should be asked. In addition to acute COPD exacerbations, decompensated heart failure, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, and pneumothorax should also be taken into account as potential causes. A big airway tumour is less probable. The signs and symptoms of acute exacerbations of COPD are typically comparable to those of other illnesses since they frequently come with fever or happen after contact with sick people. Vital signs evaluation and detection of respiratory distress symptoms should be part of the physical examination. symptoms of left or right heart failure should all be looked for during the cardiac examination to determine whether there is tachycardia, irregular rhythm, or any of

these conditions. Unusual mental state should prompt worries about hypercarbia.

An arterial blood gas should be performed on individuals who are experiencing respiratory distress or who have other causes to suspect hypercarbia as part of the laboratory examination.

Measuring the circulating amount of brain natriuretic peptide in patients may assist identify those with substantial left heart failure since tachycardia, increased jugular venous pressure, and peripheral edema can occur in both left and right heart failure. Antibiotic prescriptions can be decreased with no evidence of damage by using point-of-care C-reactive protein testing to direct dosing.

Only around 5% of patients will likely have their medication changed as a result of a chest radiograph, which shows abnormalities in roughly 15% of individuals. Any patient with chest discomfort, leukocytosis, a history of heart disease, or another aggravating condition should always have a chest radiograph taken. A sputum culture is often unlikely to have an impact on treatment.

Imaging Studies

Fig:2 chest-xray17

Signs of hyperinflation such as ⁽¹⁸⁾

A Hyperlucency of the lungs

B Increased rib space

C. Obtuse costophrenic angle

D. Low diaphragm (considered low if the border of the right hemidiaphragm in the midclavicular line lies at or below anterior at the end of seventh rib)

- Diaphragmatic flattening
 - Seen best on lateral films.
 - Perpendicular height < 1.5 cm indicates flattening

Other findings include:

- Saber-sheath trachea (trachea normal to level of thoracic inlet, then narrows in coronal plane)
- Increased retrosternal airspace (> 2.5 cm between sternum and ascending aorta)
- Increased length of lung (> 30 cm)
- Prominent vessels (large central pulmonary arteries if pulmonary hypertension has developed)
- vascular markings get tapered rapidly

Computed Tomography (CT) Scan:

Fig:3 computed Tomography

A. Emphysematous lesions in the parenchyma adjacent to the pleural surfaces

- Paraseptal emphysema

Other uses:

- Planned surgical procedure such as lung volume reduction or transplant, or prior to bronchoscopic lung volume reduction.
- For detecting comorbidities or differential diagnoses

Diagnostic Testing:

The diagnosis is established by spirometry showing airflow obstruction When the FEV₁ /

FVC ratio drops to less than 0.7, obstruction is present. Lower ratios, which are typically stated as a percentage of expected determined from reference data gathered for a normal population, indicate severe blockage (standardized by age, sex, height, and ethnic background). The lung volumes may show residual volume (RV) and total lung capacity (TLC). Emphysema or pulmonary hypertension patients may have lower DLCOs, depending on how many pulmonary capillary vessels involved in gas exchange have been lost.

Pulmonary Function Tests

Pulmonary function test (PFTs) are diagnostic tests to evaluate lung function clinical role of PFTs includes

- Aiding in the diagnosis of lung diseases by determining presence and severity of lung function defects
- Monitoring of lung function in patients with known lung disease

PFT measurements include

- Capacities
 - total lung capacity (TLC) - volume of air in the lungs at maximum inhalation
 - vital capacity (VC) - volume of air from maximal inspiratory effort to maximal expiratory effort
 - inspiratory capacity (IC) - volume of air from resting expiratory level to maximal inspiratory effort
 - functional residual capacity (FRC) - volume of air in the lungs after unforced tidal volume expiration
 - maximal voluntary ventilation (MVV) - maximal inspiration and expiration over 12-15 seconds

- Volumes
 - tidal volume (V_t) - volume of air from nonforced expiratory level to normal nonforced inspiratory level.
 - expiratory reserve volume (ERV) - volume of air that can be exhaled after resting expiration.
 - inspiratory reserve volume (IRV) - volume of air that can be inhaled after normal inspiration.
 - residual volume (RV) - volume of air left in the lungs after maximal expiratory effort.
 - forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1) - maximal amount of air exhaled during forceful expiration in first second from a point of maximal inspiration.
- Ratios
 - FEV1/FVC ratio - ratio of the volume of air expelled during the first second of forced expiration from maximal inspiration to the total volume of forced expiration from maximal inspiration
 - FEV1/VC ratio - similar to FEV1/FVC ratio, but the largest VC determination is used which can be obtained by slow inspiration, forced inspiration, slow expiration, or forced expiration
- Flow rates and flow-volume loops
 - peak expiratory flow (PEF) - maximum flow rate of air during forced expiration from maximal inspiration
 - forced expiratory flow 25%-75% (FEF25-75) - flow rate in the middle half

of forced expiration from maximal inspiration

- (flow-volume curve) - graphic display of the flow of air during forced expiration and forced inspiration
- bronchoprovocation testing is a method that measures bronchial hyper-responsiveness to a stimulant

Table :1 Common patterns of disease on PFTs ⁽¹⁾

Measurement	DISEASE CATEGORY	
	Obstructive	Restrictive
FVC	Normal/decreased	Decreased
FEV ₁	Decreased	Decreased
FEV/FVC	Decreased	Normal

- obstructive pattern common in
 - asthma (reversible)
 - COPD
 - bronchiolitis obliterans
 - constrictive bronchiolitis obliterans
 - sarcoidosis
 - bronchiectasis
 - cystic fibrosis (CF)
 - alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency
 - sarcoidosis

- increased DLCO common in

- obesity
- pulmonary alveolar hemorrhage
- asthma
- polycythemia

Fig :4 ⁽¹⁵⁾ Representative flow-volume loops in normal subjects (red) and COPD (blue).

Spirometry

- Spirometry reported to be most reproducible, objective, noninvasive, and readily available measurement of airflow obstruction
- Use spirometry to diagnose airflow obstruction in patients with respiratory symptoms but not to screen for airflow obstruction in patients without respiratory symptoms
- Spirometry demonstrating forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1)/forced vital capacity (FVC) ratio < 0.7 confirms diagnosis
- In addition to diagnosis of COPD, spirometry also useful for COPD severity

assessment and follow-up evaluations to inform therapeutic decisions and to identify worsening conditions.

Table 2: Classification of Airflow limitation Severity in COPD (1)

STAGE AND SEVERITY	DEFINITION
I: Mild	FEV ₁ /FVC <0.70, FEV ₁ ≥80% of predicted
II: Moderate	FEV ₁ /FVC <0.70, 50% ≤FEV ₁ <80% of predicted
III: Severe	FEV ₁ /FVC <0.70, 30% ≤FEV ₁ <50% of predicted
IV: Very severe	FEV ₁ /FVC <0.70, FEV ₁ <30% of predicted or FEV ₁ <50% of predicted plus chronic respiratory failure

INHALERS

Inhalers for COPD (Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease) have evolved over time. The history includes the development of bronchodilators and anti-inflammatory medications delivered through various inhaler devices. Early inhalers used chloroform, but advancements led to the introduction of metered-dose inhalers (MDIs) in the 1950s. In 1969, the pharmaceutical company Allen & Hanburys (now part of GlaxoSmithKline) introduced the first salbutamol inhaler under the brand name Ventolin.⁽²⁸⁾ The inhaler became a breakthrough in the treatment of asthma, providing rapid relief by relaxing the smooth muscles in the airways.⁽²⁹⁾ The 1990s saw the rise of dry powder inhalers (DPIs) and newer formulations. Today, a variety of inhalers, including combination therapies, offer improved symptom management for COPD patients.^(30,31)

In the 1990s, long-acting bronchodilators, including long-acting beta-agonists (LABAs) and

long-acting anticholinergics (LAMAs), gained prominence. Combining LABAs and inhaled corticosteroids became a common strategy for managing COPD.

Advancements continued with the introduction of dual bronchodilator therapy, combining LABAs and LAMAs, providing enhanced bronchodilation. These medications have played a crucial role in improving symptom control, exercise tolerance, and overall quality of life for COPD patients. Ongoing research aims to refine treatment approaches and develop new bronchodilators to address the diverse needs of individuals with COPD.^(32,33)

HISTORY OF INHALERS

Early Years: In the 1950s, the first bronchodilators, such as theophylline, were introduced for COPD. Theophylline is a methylxanthine compound that helps relax the smooth muscles of the airways, improving airflow.⁽³⁴⁾

Beta-Adrenergic Agonists: In the 1960s, beta-adrenergic agonists like albuterol were introduced. These medications act on beta receptors in the lungs, leading to bronchodilation and improved breathing.⁽³⁵⁾

Anticholinergics: The 1970s saw the development of anticholinergic bronchodilators, like ipratropium bromide. These drugs block the action of acetylcholine, a neurotransmitter that constricts airway smooth muscles.⁽³⁶⁾

Combination Therapies: Over time, combination therapies became prevalent, involving both short-acting and long-acting bronchodilators to provide sustained relief for COPD patients.

Long-Acting Beta-Agonists (LABAs) and Long-Acting Anticholinergics (LAMAs): In the late 20th century and early 21st century, long-acting bronchodilators such as LABAs and LAMAs were developed to offer prolonged effects and reduce the frequency of inhaler use.⁽³⁷⁾

Dual Bronchodilation: More recently, dual bronchodilation therapies combining LABAs and

LAMAs have become a standard treatment approach for moderate to severe COPD.

The continuous evolution of bronchodilators reflects ongoing efforts to enhance efficacy, minimize side effects, and improve the overall management of COPD. These medications remain a cornerstone in alleviating symptoms and enhancing the quality of life for individuals with COPD.⁽³⁸⁾

Salbutamol inhalers, commonly known as rescue inhalers, have a history dating back to the 1960s. Salbutamol, a type of short-acting beta-2 adrenergic agonist, was first synthesized by British pharmacologist Sir David Jack. The inhaler form of salbutamol gained popularity for its effectiveness in relieving bronchospasm, a common symptom in conditions like asthma
(39,40)

PRINCIPLES OF DEPOSITION⁽⁴¹⁾

- The term "Deposition fraction" refers to the portion of inhaled particles that deposit rather than expel.
- Relies on how three factors interact:

The particle's physical properties, such as its mass and shape

The patient's breathing pattern and any propellant-provided velocity in the gas flow in which the particle is moved; and the anatomy of the airways (particularly the presence of airway obstruction).

Inertial Impaction:

Describes the process by which a particle hits a barrier rather than avoiding it because it is unable to follow the air flowing in which it is suspended.

Owing to the momentum created, sizable particles, around 20 μm in size, are deposited in the oropharyngeal area instead of following the airway's anatomical course.

Sedimentation:

When particles with sizes ranging from 0.5 μm to 5 μm stay in the lower airways long enough for sedimentation to occur, they are deposited there by gravity.

- The optimal range of particle sizes to provide the desired therapeutic effect is 2 μm to 5 μm .

Diffusion⁽⁴²⁾

Particles less than 0.5 μm move randomly at the alveolar surface because of the Brownian diffusion effect. At the conclusion of expiration, these particles are either ejected out or diffuse across the alveolar membrane into the bloodstream.

ADVERSE EFFECTS OF INHALERS ^(43,44)

Dysphonia

because of inflammatory infiltrates in the mucosa, supraglottic hyperfunction, or bilateral adductor myopathy.

Oropharyngeal candidiasis

3% of people get this side effect after using inhaled corticosteroids because of their immunosuppressive qualities.

The Cold-Freon Effect

The temperature of the aerosol decreases to around -30°C when the propellant, which is under pressure in the canister, is let out via the nozzle; by the time it reaches the throat, the temperature has dropped to about 0°C .

- It can be readily overcome with the use of a spacer; in some patients, it induces pharyngeal spasm and encourages coughing when it reaches the throat at 0°C .
- Patients on Inhaled corticosteroids develop side effects such as thrush (oral fungal infection), hoarseness, sore throat, increased risk of cataracts and osteoporosis with

long-term use (especially at high doses).

- Patients on long acting muscarinic antagonists develop side effects such as Dry mouth, constipation, urinary retention (especially in elderly patients), blurred vision.

DRUGS USED IN INHALERS ⁽⁴⁵⁾

LABAs were introduced for asthma treatment in 1990 and over time have become widely used in both asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD).

Inhaled β 2-agonists⁽⁴⁶⁾ are classified as:

- Short-acting (SABAs), with a rapid onset of effect in the airways but a relatively short duration of action (3 to 4 hours)'
- Includes: Albuterol, Bitolterol, Orciprenaline, Pirbuterol, Terbutaline Fenoterol
- Long-acting (LABAs), with a 12- to 24-hour duration of activity.
- Includes salmeterol, formoterol , Bambuterol , Clenbuterol
- Ultralong-acting (ultra-LABAs), with a duration of activity of at least 24 hours.
Includes Indacaterol , Arformoterol Oldaterol and vilanterol
- Long-acting β 2 -selective agonists includes salmeterol (a partial agonist) and formoterol (a full agonist).
- Both drugs are potent selective β 2 agonists that achieve their long duration of action (12 hours or more) because of high lipid solubility.
- This permits them to dissolve in the smooth muscle cell membrane in high concentrations or, possibly, attach to “mooring” molecules in the vicinity of adrenoreceptors.
- Formoterol initially was developed as an oral β 2-agonist and its long duration of activity when inhaled was discovered by chance.

- Binding of formoterol is similar to that of epinephrine to the β_2 -receptor, the nature of salmeterol binding remains controversial.
- The main difference between the two LABA drugs is that salmeterol is intrinsically long acting, whereas the duration of action of formoterol is critically dependent on its route of administration

MECHANISM OF ACTION ⁽⁴⁷⁾

- Beta-2 agonists are G protein-linked second messengers.
- The Gs protein stimulates adenylyl cyclase, which converts ATP to cAMP. Subsequently, cAMP activates protein kinase A, which inhibits myosin light chain kinase (present in smooth muscle).
- This cascade results in the relaxation of bronchiolar smooth muscle, bronchodilation, and increased bronchiole airflow

COPD:

- Long acting beta2 agonists are superior to short acting ones and equivalent to inhaled anticholinergics in copd . They reduce breathlessness by abolishing the reversible component of airway obstruction.
- Formoterol and salmeterol are twice daily LABA that significantly that significantly improves FEV1 and lung volumes dyspnoea exacerbations.
- Indacaterol is once daily LABA that improves breathlessness health status and exacerbation rates
- Oldaterol and vilanterol are additional once daily LABA that improve lung function.

MECHANISM OF ACTION of Muscarinic antagonist ⁽⁴⁸⁾

- SAMA namely ipratropium and oxitropium also block the inhibitory neuronal receptor

M2 which potentially can cause vagally induced bronchoconstriction.

- Long-acting muscarinic antagonists such as tiotropium, aclidinium, glycopyrrolate, and umeclidinium have prolonged binding to M3 muscarinic receptors with faster dissociation from M2 muscarinic receptors thus prolonging the duration of bronchodilator effect.
- Glycopyrronium is a synthetic quaternary ammonium congener of atropine with a distinct molecular structure

Absorption

- Absolute bioavailability: 40%
- Peak plasma time: 5 minutes

Distribution

- Protein bound: 38-41%
- Vd: 83-376 L

Metabolism

- Hydroxylated to a variety of mono- and bis-hydroxylated metabolites and direct hydrolysis results in the formation of a carboxylic acid derivative (M9)
- M9 is hydrolyzed by multiple CYP isoenzymes

Elimination

- Half-life: 33-53 hr (glycopyrrolate inhaled)
- Excretion: 60-70% urine; 30-40% nonrenal (mostly by metabolism; also biliary)

Adverse effect:

- Dry mouth, urinary retention, blurred vision, dry skin

MMRC GRADING

- Modified Medical Research Council (mMRC) questionnaire, which evaluates

breathlessness based on scale of 0-4

- grade 0: patient breathless with strenuous exercise
- grade 1: patient short of breath when hurrying on level ground or walking up slight hill
- grade 2: patient walks slower than same-age peers due to breathlessness, or has to stop for breath when walking at own pace on level ground
- grade 3: patient stops to catch breath after walking about 100 meters or after a few minutes on level ground.
- grade 4: patient too breathless to leave the house or breathless when dressing or undressing.

Clinical COPD questionnaire:

The Clinical COPD Questionnaire (CCQ) has three categories and ten items with scores ranging from 0 to 6. (symptoms, functional, mental).⁽⁴⁹⁾ Adding together the individual item scores and dividing them by ten yields the total score, which ranges from 0 to 6, with higher scores denoting lower HRQoL.

After totaling together all of the answers and dividing by the total number of questions—10 in this case—the final score is determined. In a similar manner, domains are determined by aggregating the responses for each domain, dividing by 4 for the functional domain and symptom, and dividing by 2 for the mental domain.⁴ The CCQ values can be classified as follows: very instable-very severe limited ($CCQ \geq 3$), acceptable ($CCQ < 1$), acceptable for moderate disease ($1 \leq CCQ < 2$), and instable-severe limited ($2 \leq CCQ < 3$).^(50,51)

According to several recent studies that have proposed the CAT as a simpler, more practical alternative HRQoL measure to time-consuming questionnaires like the CRQ and SGRQ, the adoption of a quicker health status questionnaire could result in more effective service

delivery and subsequent cost savings.^(51,52,53) Compared to more well-known surveys, the CCQ takes far less time and staff involvement to complete⁽⁵⁴⁾, but it could possibly give more information due to the inclusion of domain and overall scores. Recent studies also seem to indicate that there is a modest preference for the CCQ over the CAT at the patient and clinician level^(51,52,53)

COPD ASSESSMENT TEST:

Eight items make up the CAT, which concentrates on respiratory symptoms like cough, sputum production, tightness in the chest, and dyspnea as well as non-respiratory symptoms like fatigue or sleep disturbances and additional indicators like difficulty performing tasks at home or lack of confidence leaving the house.⁽⁵⁴⁾

As to the findings of Jones et al., the item "breathlessness" exhibits the highest discriminating power for milder patients, while the item "confidence leaving home" exhibits superior discriminating power for more severe patients.⁽⁵⁴⁾

CAT total score determines the GOLD classification of patients with COPD (classifying patients into low (A/C) and high (B/D) symptom groups) and, in turn, the recommended respiratory pharmacological treatment strategy.⁽¹⁾

It's critical to comprehend how the CAT score is calculated and how each individual item contributes. Overall, there were strong connections between item and overall scores. Only 44.7% of patients with a CAT total score of fewer than 10 points, however, reported having more severe symptoms (>3 points) on 3 or 4 of the respiratory categories, including "cough," "phlegm," "chest tightness," and "breathlessness."⁽⁵⁴⁾

SIX MINUTE WALK TEST:

A straightforward cardiopulmonary functional assessment method is the six-minute walk test. Its simplicity enables an integrative, non-specific evaluation of the several systems engaged

during physical exercise. In particular, its findings may help determine the level of functional impairment and might influence how various cardiovascular and pulmonary disorders are treated.

The primary physiological phenomena pertinent to the test are the exchanges between the heart and lungs during exercise. Generally speaking, deoxygenated blood returns to the right heart through the veins pushed into the pulmonary circulation by the right ventricle. Gas exchange takes place when the blood travels through the lung capillaries, with oxygen entering the bloodstream and carbon dioxide being discharged into the alveoli.

The left ventricle of the left heart then pumps oxygenated blood into the systemic circulation, which finally transports it to the organs to support aerobic metabolism. This process also involves the neurological or musculoskeletal systems, particularly when it comes to the process of adjusting minute breathing to cardiac function in response to changing exercise levels of intensity. This happens as a result of reflex actions that modify pulmonary and cardiac activity to match the amounts of oxygen consumption required by the level of effort.

The Total distance walked is the main test result (6MWD).^[55] The typical 6MWD in healthy people ranges from 400 to 700 meters.

While 6MWD is closely correlated with worse life quality indices, respiratory and impaired functioning, and survival, it has been proven as a relevant index of symptom severity for COPD patients.

The primary test outcome is the final distance walked (6MWD).⁽⁵⁵⁾ Among healthy individuals, the average 6MWD is between 400 and 700 meters.

6MWD has been established as a significant marker of disease severity for COPD patients since it directly correlates with lower quality of life indices, respiratory and functional impairment, and survival.^(56,57)

BODE INDEX

A multistage scoring system called the BODE index (Body mass index, airway obstruction, dyspnea, and exercise capacity) was developed by Celli et al.⁽⁵⁸⁾ in 2004 as a death prediction index. It offers helpful prognostic information for patients with COPD.⁽⁵⁸⁾ Two-year mortality rates of 30%, 15%, and 10%, respectively, are linked to BODE scores of seven or above, five or six, and less than five. Research has demonstrated that the BODE index is a more accurate indicator of death risk among COPD patients than the FEV1.⁽⁵⁹⁾ The BODE index may be a sensitive technique for predicting the HRQoL in COPD patients, but this is not well understood. HRQoL is a patient-reported outcome questionnaire, meaning that the patient self-administers the questionnaires and completes them to provide direct feedback.⁽⁶⁰⁾

STUDIES OF COMPARISON OF INHALERS ON COPD

In 2021 a study was published in Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease conducted by Sophie Dell'Aniello & Pierre Ernst⁽⁶¹⁾ did a study on LABA/LAMA fixed-dose combinations versus LAMA monotherapy in the prevention of COPD exacerbations and compared the effectiveness of LABA/LAMA fixed-dose combinations (FDCs) versus LAMA monotherapy in preventing exacerbations of COPD . LABA/LAMA FDCs were found to significantly reduce the rate of moderate to severe exacerbations compared to LAMA monotherapy. This suggests that the combination therapy offers superior efficacy in preventing exacerbations, which is a critical outcome in managing COPD and LABA/LAMA FDCs were also associated with improved symptom control and lung function compared to LAMA monotherapy. This improvement in lung function can lead to better overall quality of life for COPD patients.

In 2020 a study was published in therapeutic advances in respiratory diseases by Ching – Yen

Chan⁽⁶²⁾ stated that LABA/LAMA fixed-dose combinations were found to significantly reduce the rate of COPD exacerbations compared to LAMA monotherapy. This reduction is attributed to the synergistic bronchodilatory effects of combining a long-acting beta agonist (LABA) with a long-acting muscarinic antagonist (LAMA). The meta-analysis likely demonstrated statistically significant findings favoring LABA/LAMA combinations in terms of exacerbation prevention.

In 2019 a study was conducted by Samy Suissa, Sophie Dell’Aniello, and Pierre Ernst, published in CHEST⁽⁶³⁾ which sheds light on the comparative effectiveness and safety of LABA-LAMA (combination of long-acting beta-agonist and long-acting muscarinic antagonist) versus LABA-ICS (combination of long-acting beta-agonist and inhaled corticosteroid) therapies for COPD in real-world clinical practice. This study supports the efficacy of LABA-LAMA therapy in reducing COPD exacerbations and suggests a favorable safety profile with respect to cardiovascular events compared to LABA-ICS therapy. These findings contribute to evidence-based decision-making in the management of COPD, emphasizing the importance of tailoring treatment strategies to optimize patient outcomes.

In 2018 IMPACT study was published in New England Journal of Medicine by Lipson et al⁽⁶⁴⁾ it was a 3, randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, multicenter trial comparing single inhaler therapy and the beneficial effects of ICS/LABA/LAMA combination compared with LABA/LAMA therapy were larger in patients with a blood eosinophil count of 150 cells/ul. or greater compared to those who had counts lower than this level (32% relative reduction vs. 12%).

In 2017 a study conducted by Suissa, Dell’Aniello, and Ernst⁽⁶⁵⁾ investigated the initiation of long-acting bronchodilators in patients diagnosed with COPD, focusing particularly on the

potential risks of adverse cardiopulmonary events. Their study analyzed a cohort of patients to assess whether there is an increased risk of adverse events such as cardiovascular events or exacerbations of COPD following the initiation of these medications. This study correlates that the initiation of long-acting bronchodilators in COPD patients did not significantly increase the risk of adverse cardiopulmonary events compared to baseline or to non-initiators.

Conclusion was drawn after controlling for various confounding factors such as age, sex, smoking status, and comorbidities. The authors suggest that the benefits of using long-acting bronchodilators in improving lung function and reducing symptoms outweigh the potential risks observed in their study cohort. This study provides valuable insights into the safety profile of long-acting bronchodilators in COPD patients, emphasizing their role in improving respiratory outcomes without significantly increasing the risk of adverse cardiopulmonary events.

In 2017 Horita N and Goto A conducted a study on "Long-acting muscarinic antagonist (LAMA) plus long-acting β -agonist (LABA) versus LABA plus inhaled corticosteroid (ICS) for stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)"⁽⁶⁶⁾ they concluded that combining a LAMA with a LABA may provide benefits comparable to or better than those of a LABA combined with an ICS for stable COPD. The review found evidence suggesting that LAMA + LABA therapy could reduce the risk of exacerbations and improve lung function without increasing the risk of adverse events compared to LABA + ICS therapy. These findings underscored the efficacy and safety of LAMA + LABA combination therapy as a viable treatment option for managing stable COPD.

In 2017 Clauss Vogelmeir stated in the New England Journal of medicine that Tiotropium (LAMA) has a minor advantage over salmeterol (LABA) for the prevention of exacerbations, despite the fact that both LABAs and LAMAs have similar effects, according to the

Prevention of Exacerbations in Tiotropium (POET) study⁽⁶⁷⁾. Compared to those who took salmeterol, those who were prescribed tiotropium had an average 17% decreased risk of exacerbation during a one-year period. Interestingly, patients with GOLD grade 4 disease severity and those with a body mass index (BMI) of less than 20 kg/30< m² showed the highest relative risk difference in exacerbation between the tiotropium and salmeterol arms of the research. For tiotropium, the person-based net new prescriptions (NNT) was 25 patients annually; however, for these two patient groupings, the NNT was only 8.

In 2016 FLAME study was published in New England Journal Of Medicine by Wedzicha and et al⁽⁶⁸⁾ and stated that The FLAME study concluded that IND/GLY (Indacaterol–Glycopyrronium) provides superior efficacy in reducing exacerbations compared to SFC (Salmeterol–Fluticasone) in patients with COPD. This suggests that long acting LABA LAMA may offer a better treatment option for preventing exacerbations and managing symptoms in COPD patients when compared with LABA ICS and this study also The safety profiles of both treatments were generally comparable, with no significant differences in adverse events.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SOURCE OF DATA:

COPD patients visiting the Department of Respiratory Medicine, B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura will be included in this study.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA:

Study Design: Randomized Control Trial

Study Period: Two Years

Study Sample :70 COPD. Patients (35 patients on LABA- LAMA , 35 patients on LABA – ICS)

Inclusion criteria

- Patients willing to give informed consent.
- Patients aged above 40 years
- Patients of either sex.

Exclusion criteria

- Patient unwilling to give informed consent.
- Pregnant and lactating women.
- Patient is not willing to Inhalational treatment.
- Patient is not willing for Spirometry.

All diagnosed cases of COPD will be included in this R.C.T. study, and baseline assessment of COPD QOL, and Spirometry will be done. Following which patient will be assigned to

either LABA+ICS or LABA+LAMA group. And accordingly, the treatment will be started. Q.O.L. will be assessed by M.M.R.C., C.A.T. Score, and COPD Combined assessment. Spirometry will be performed using N.D.D. Easy one Pro advanced spirometry machine. The patient will be followed up every third months for six months. Q.O.L. and Spirometry will be reassessed. And any history of side effects will be enquired. All the data will be updated in the proforma and used while preparing the master chart and analysis.

Statistical Analysis

- The data obtained will be entered in a Microsoft Excel sheet, and statistical analysis will be performed using a statistical package for the social sciences (Version 20).
- Results will be presented as Mean \pm SD, Median and interquartile range, frequency, percentages and diagrams.
- For normally distributed continuous variables between two groups will be compared using independent t-test For not normally distributed variables, Mann Whitney U test will be used.
- Categorical variables between two groups will be compared using the Chi-square test/Fisher's Exact test.
- P,0.005 will be considered statistically significant. All statistical tests will perform two-tailed.

RESULTS

TABLE NO 3: NUMBER OF PATIENTS IN EACH GROUP

TYPE OF INHALER	FM-BD	FM-GP
NUMBER OF PATIENTS IN EACH GROUP	35	35

FLOW CHART – NUMBER OF PATIENTS IN EACH GROUP AND ON FOLLOW UP

Due to time constraints in view of completing dissertation follow up visit of all patients was reduced to 3 months from 6 months

AGE DISTRIBUTION

The distribution of patients according to different age groups in two groups is depicted below with majority of patients in both groups being between the age group of 60-69. The mean age is 64.41 and 64.75 in FM-BD and FM-GP group respectively.

GRAPH 2 : AGE DISTRIBUTION BETWEEN FM-BD AND FM-GP GROUP

GENDER DISTRIBUTION

Majority of the patients in the study were male and gender distribution in both groups was similar to each other.

TABLE 4 : GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF COPD PATIENTS

SEX	MALE	FEMALE
NUMBER OF PATIENTS	48	22

BMI DISTRIBUTION

Mean BMI is 21.28 and 21.57 in FM-BD and FM-GP group respectively

TABLE 5 :PATIENTS BASED ON BMI LESS THAN OR EQUAL TO 21

BMI	<21	>21
NUMBER OF PATIENTS	33	37

SMOKING PACK YEARS

TABLE 6: PATIENTS DISTRIBUTED BASED ON DURATION OF PACK YEARS

PACK YEARS	<10	11-19	20-29	30-39	>40
NUMBER OF PATIENTS	19	5	15	2	7

GRAPH 3: GRADING OF COPD PATIENTS WITH RESPECTIVE PACK YEARS

The above graph depicts that patients with pack years above 20 years are prone to develop Severe COPD.

BIOMASS EXPOURE

TABLE 7: NUMBER OF PATIENTS WITH BIOMASS EXPOSURE MORE THAN 20 YEARS

NUMBER OF BIOMASS EXPOURE YEARS	<20	>20
NUMBER OF PATIENTS	9	13

GRAPH 4: COPD GRADING WITH YEARS OF BIOMASS EXPOSURE

The above graph depicts that patients with biomass exposure of more than 20 years are more prone to have Severe COPD.

MMRC GRADING

TABLE 8: SEVERITY OF COPD AND MMRC GRADING IN FM-BD GROUP

FEV1% Predicted	MMRC 4	MMRC 3	MMRC 2
0-30 (very severe)	12	1	0
31-50 (severe)	13	6	0
51-80 (moderate)	0	2	0
>80 (mild)	0	0	0

TABLE 9:SEVERITY OF COPD AND MMRC GRADING IN FM-GP GROUP

FEV1% Predicted	MMRC 4	MMRC 3	MMRC 2
0-30 (very severe)	9	0	0
31-50 (severe)	16	4	0
51-80 (moderate)	2	4	0
>80 (mild)	0	1	0

GRAPH 5: Change of MMRC Grading of both the groups after two visits from Grade 4 to either Grade 3 or Grade 2

The above graph depicts that patients with Very Severe COPD when started on FM-BD 25% changed from Grade 4 MMRC to Grade 3 or Grade 2 whereas 66.6% similar shift was seen in FM-GP group. Patients with Severe COPD when started on inhalers conversion from Grade 4 to lower grade was seen in 76.9% and 87.5 % of patients in FM-BD and FM-GP group respectively.

TABLE 10: CHANGE IN MEAN MMRC SCORE IN BOTH GROUPS AFTER TWO VISITS

	FM-BD	FM-GP
MEAN MMRC GRADING	0.56 ± 0.61	0.89± 0.75
STATSTICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Mann Whitney test)	P- 0.019	

Change in Mean MMRC Grading was statistically significant with increased change in FM-GP group when compared to FM-BD group. Patients in FM-GP group showed more improvement in their MMRC grading when compared to FM- BD group in our study.

CAT SCORE

TABLE 11: CAT SCORE IN FM-BD GROUP AND FM- GP GROUP AFTER TWO VISITS

MEAN CAT SCORE	FIRST VISIT	SECOND VISIT
FM-BD GROUP	29.47	23.47
CLINICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.001	
FM-GP GROUP	28.58	21.81

<p>CLINICALLY SIGNIFICANT</p> <p>(As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)</p>	<p>P- 0.001</p>
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GRAPH 6: MEAN CAT SCORES IN FM-BD ND FM-GP GROUPS AFTER TWO VISITS

TABLE 12:MEAN CHANGE IN CAT SCORE IN BOTH GROUPS AFTER TWO VISITS

MEAN CAT GRADING	FM-BD	FM-GP
FM-BD GROUP	4.21 ± 2.26	4.17 ± 2.02
CLINICALLY INSIGNIFICANT (As per Mann Whitney test)	P- 0.72	

CCQ SCORE

TABLE 13 :CCQ SCORE IN FM-BD GROUP AND FM-GP GROUP AFTER TWO VISITS

MEAN CCQ GRADING	FIRST VISIT	SECOND VISIT
FM-BD GROUP	3.336 ± 0.94	2.650 ± 0.76
CLINICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.001	
FM-GP GROUP	3.153 ± 0.33	2.45 ± 0.80
STASTICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.001	

GRAPH 7: MEAN CCQ SCORE IN BOTH THE GROUPS IN 2 VISITS

TABLE 14: CHANGE IN MEAN CCQ SCORE IN BOTH GROUPS AFTER TWO VISITS

	FM-BD	FM-GP
CHANGE IN MEAN CCQ SCORE	1.05 ± 0.9	0.49 ± 0.24
CLINICALLY INSIGNIFICANT (As per Mann Whitney test)	P- 0.93	

POST BRONCHODILATOR FEV1 PREDICTED

Based on Post Bronchodilator FEV1 Predicted majority of patients in both the groups were in Severe and very Severe COPD ,

GRAPH 8 :NUMBER OF COPD PATIENTS GRADED BASED ON COPD SEVERITY

TABLE 15: POST BRONCHODILATOR FEV1 PREDICTED IN FM-BD GROUP AND FM- GP GROUP AFTER TWO VISITS

MEAN FEV1 PREDICTED	FIRST VISIT	SECOND VISIT
FM-BD GROUP	34 ± 11.68	33.59 ± 13.33
CLINICALLY INSIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.24	
FM-GP GROUP	39.53 ± 16.33	40.08 ± 19.53
CLINICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.01	

GRAPH 9: MEAN POST BRONCHODILATOR FEV1 %PREDICTED OF BOTH FM-BD GROUP AND FM-GP GROUP IN FIRST AND SECOND VISIT

TABLE 16: CHANGE IN MEAN FEV1 % PREDICTED IN BOTH GROUPS FM-BD

GROUP AFTER TWO VISITS

CHANGE IN MEAN FEV1% PREDICTED	FB-BD	FM-GP
FM- BD GROUP	3.18 ± 2.05	4.06± 2.48
CLINICALLY INSIGNIFICANT (As per Mann Whitney test)	P- 0.103	

POST BRONCHODILATOR FVC%

TABLE 17: POST BRONCHODILATOR FVC% IN FM-BD GROUP AND FM-GP

GROUP AFTER TWO VISITS

POST BRONCHODILATOR FVC%	FIRST VISIT	SECOND VISIT
FM-BD GROUP	50.94 ± 13.12	47.5 ± 17.86
CLINICALLY INSIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.53	
FM-GP GROUP	53.3 ± 15.7	50.83 ± 20.57
CLINICALLY INSIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.066	

TABLE 18:CHANGE IN POST BRONCHODILATOR FVC% IN BOTH GROUPS

AFTER TWO VISITS

	FM-BD	FM-GP
CHANGE IN MEAN FVC%	4.476 ± 5.55	2.72 ± 2.008
CLINICALLY INSIGNIFICANT (As per Mann Whitney test)	P- 0.103	

TABLE 19: POST BRONCHODILATOR CHANGE IN FEV1%

POST BRONCHODILATOR CHANGE IN FEV1% IN FM-BD AND FM-GP GROUP

AFTER TWO VISITS

POST BRONCHODILATOR CHANGE IN FEV1%	FIRST VISIT	SECOND VISIT
FM-BD GROUP	14.75 ± 10.8	8.50 ± 7.22
CLINICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.01	
FM-GP GROUP	11.11 ± 15.7	7.50 ± 6.13
CLINICALLY INSIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P -0.66	

POST BRONCHODILATOR CHANGE IN FEV1% IN FM-GP GROUP AFTER TWO VISITS

GRAPH 10: POST BRONCHODILATOR MEAN FEV1% CHANGE IN BOTH GROUPS

TABLE 20 :CHANGE IN MEAN FEV1% CHANGE POST BRONCHODILATOR AFTER TWO VISITS IN FM-BD AND FM-GP GROUP

	FM-BD	FM-GP
CHANGE IN MEAN FEV1% CHANGE	8.71 ± 7.705	4.06 ± 2.48
CLINICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Mann Whitney test)	P- 0.008	

There is positive correlation between Delta mean Fev1 change between the two groups, with increased change in Delta mean FEV1 in FM-BD group than FM-GP group and is statistically significant with p value of 0.008 from Mann Whitney U test.

SIX MINUTE WALK TEST

TABLE 21 : DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENT BASED ON DISTANCE COVERED AFTER 6 MINUTES

DISTANCE IN METERS	>149	150-249	250-349	>350
NUMBER OF PATIENTS	25	35	10	0

TABLE 22: CHANGE IN 6MWT IN FM-BD GROUP AND FM-GP GROUP AFTER TWO VISITS

CHANGE IN 6MWT	FIRST VISIT	SECOND VISIT
FM-BD GROUP	169.71 ± 56.12	200.00 ± 87.97
STATISTICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.001	
FM-GP GROUP	182.72 ± 47.48	226.94 ± 86.36
STATISTICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P- 0.001	

GRAPH 11: MEAN 6MWT AFTER TWO VISITS IN BOTH GROUPS

TABLE 23: MEAN 6MWT CHANGE AFTER TWO VISITS IN FM-BD AND FM-GP

GROUP

	FM-BD	FM-GP
MEAN CHANGE IN 6MWT AFTER 2 VISITS	50.15 ± 27.47	57.22 ± 30.94
STATISTICALLY INSIGNIFICANT (As per Mann Whitney test)	P- 0.400	

BODE INDEX

TABLE 24: CHANGE IN BODE INDEX (SCORE) IN FM-BD GROUP AFTER TWO VISITS

CHANGE IN BODE INDEX	FIRST VISIT	SECOND VISIT
FM-BD GROUP	7.88 ± 1.80	6.53± 2.22
STATISTICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P-0.001	
FM-GP GROUP	7.78 ± 1.80	5.06± 2.21
STATISTICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Wilcoxon signed rank test)	P-0.001	

GRAPH 12:MODE BODE INDEX AFTER TWO VISIST IN BOTH GROUPS

TABLE 25: BODE INDEX IN BOTH GROUPS IN BOTH VISITS

FIRST VISIT	<7	>7	SECOND VISIT	<7	>7
FM-BD	8	27	FM-BD	14	19
FM-GP	7	28	FM-GP	24	8

% Change of BODE of both the groups after two visits from BODE ≥ 7 to BODE < 7

The above table depicts that 23.7% and 44.4% of VERY SEVERE COPD patients in FM-BD and FM-GP group after 3 months had reduction in BODE INDEX to less than 7 respectively. In SEVERE COPD patients 38.4 % and 83.3% in FM-BD and FM-GP group after 3 months had reduction in BODE INDEX to less than 7 respectively

TABLE 26: MEAN BODE CHANGE AFTER TWO VISITS IN FM-BD AND FM-GP

GROUP

	FM-BD	FM-GP
MEAN CHANGE IN BODE AFTER 2 VISITS	0.91 \pm 0.965	1.97 \pm 1.108
STATISTICALLY SIGNIFICANT (As per Mann Whitney test)	P- 0.04	

Mean change in BODE Index significantly improved in FM-GP group when compared to FM-BD group.

TABLE 27: ADVERSE EFFECTS OF FM-BD AND FM-GP GROUP AFTER 2 VISITS

ADVERSE EFFECTS	FM-BD	FM-GP
DRY MOUTH	2 (6.25%)	5 (15.1%)
DYSPHONIA	4 (12.5%)	2 (6%)
ORAL CADIDAISIS	5 (15.6%)	0
TACHYCARDIA	5 (15.6%)	3 (9.09%)
TREMORS	6 (18.75%)	4 (12.5%)
HEADACHE	5 (15.6%)	2 (6.25%)
ANEXITY	3 (9.3%)	0
HOARSNESS	6 (18.75%)	1 (3.12%)

GRAPH 13: ADVERSE EFFECTS IN BOTH THE GROUPS AFER 2 VIISTS

TABLE 28 :Number of exacerbations in both groups (within 3 months of first visit)

GROUPS	FM-BD	FM-GP
NUMBER OF PATIENTS WITH EXACERBATIONS WITHIN 3 MONTHS	06 (18.75%)	02 (6.25%)

GRAPH 14:NUMBER OF EXACERBATIONS BASED ON COPD GRADING

TABLE 29 :Number of hospitalisations following exacerbations (within 3 months of first visit)

GROUPS	FM-BD	FM-GP
NUMBER OF WARD ADMISSIONS	4	1
NUMBER OF ICU ADMISSIONS	2	1

TABLE 30: Number of deaths (within 3 months of first visit)

GROUPS	FM-BD	FM-GP
NUMBER OF DEATHS	1	0

One female patient age 68 years old in FM-BD group a known case of Cor Pulmonale after 2 months of initiation of inhaler developed a exacerbation for which patient was hospitalized and suffered a cardiopulmonary arrest after which she succumbed to death.

DISCUSSION

In this study 70 COPD patients were first diagnosed after PFT evaluation and were randomized and allocated into two groups of FM-BD and FM-GP.

Patients were evaluated initially with Spirometry, and CAT score, CCQ score and BODE index. On follow up 32 patients were evaluated in FM-BD group and 33 IN FM-GP group

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

Around 69% patients enrolled in this trial were male reflecting a common trend in COPD demographics. Both groups have a similar age distribution centered around 60-69 years, which is typical for COPD patients.(Graph 2)

The mean age is 64.41 and 64.75 in FM-BD and FM-GP group respectively.

The mean BMI is 21.28 and 21.57 in FM-BD and FM-GP group respectively.

Both age and BMI when compared between groups was statistically insignificant when compared using Independent T test. Rabe et al⁽⁵⁾ in 2020 when compared both the groups had similar mean age of 64.8 and 64.6 in GM-GP and FM- BD respectively.

Tashkin et al⁽⁶⁹⁾ in 2016 conducted a similar study comparing the same inhalers with mean age in FM-BD and FM-GP groups 63.8 and 61.8 respectively.

Singh ET al in 2015⁽⁷⁰⁾ when compared COPD patients with into similar groups, this study mean age in both the groups was 61.4 and 61.8 respectively with mean BMI in both groups 27.6 and 27.2 respectively which was slightly higher when compared to our study.

SMOKING PACK YEARS

More than 65 % of 48 patients with history of smoking have smoking pack years of more than 20 years. Majority of patients with pack years of more than 20 were having Severe to Very Severe COPD. There is a clear trend that patients with higher pack years (> 20) are more

prone to developing severe COPD, highlighting smoking as a significant risk factor. (Graph3)

Average pack years was 37.5 and 38.2 years in FM-BD and FM – GP groups respectively.

ETHOS trial⁽⁵⁾ when compared the similar groups has a mean smoking pack years of 47 and 48 years in the respective FM-BD and FM-GP groups.

Singh et al⁽⁷⁰⁾ when compared similar two groups has average pack years of 39 and 40 years respectively in this study.

BIOMASS EXPOSURE

22 female patients enrolled in this study and more than half of them had biomass exposure of more than or equal to 20 years. Patients with more than 20 years of biomass exposure also show a higher propensity for severe COPD, indicating another important risk factor in this population.(Table 7)

In our study most of the patients on initial evaluation were categorized into severe and very severe categories based on FEV1 % predicted when compared to other studies, Montegouda et al⁽⁷⁴⁾ when compared similar groups had majority of patients in moderate COPD category , Rabe et al in their study had similar data to our study with more than 60% patients being in severe COPD category.

TABLE 31 : DEMOGRAPHIC DATA OF SIMILAR STUDIES

<u>AUTHOR AND YEAR</u>	<u>STUDY DESIGN</u>	<u>MEAN AGE IN FM-BD</u>	<u>MEAN AGE IN FM-GP BMI</u>	<u>MEAN PACK YEARS IN FM-BD</u>	<u>MEAN PACK YEARS IN FM-GP GROUP</u>	<u>MEAN BMI IN FM -BD GROUP</u>	<u>MEAN BMI IN FM-GP GROUP</u>
RABE ET AL 2020 ⁽⁵⁾	RCT	64.6	64.8	47.1	48.4	22.5	21.9

HANIA ET AL 2018 ⁽⁷¹⁾	RCT	62.9	62.7	35.6	36.5	22.6	22.8
WEDZICHA ET AL 2016 ⁽⁶⁸⁾	RCT	64.5	64.6	38.2	39.2	23.6	23.2
<u>SINGH ET AL 2015⁽⁷⁰⁾</u>	RCT	61.4	61.8	40.2	40.6	27.2	27.6
OUR STUDY	RCT	64.41	64.57	19.8	19.6	21.28	21.57

DISCUSSION ON PRIMARY OBJECTIVES

1) TO DETERMINE CHANGES IN SPIROMETRY IN FM-BD AND FM-GP GROUPS

TABLE 32 : SPIROMETRIC DATA OF SIMILAR STUDIES

<u>AUTHOR AND YEAR</u>	<u>STUDY DESIGN</u>	<u>MEAN FEV1%PR ED IN FM-BD</u>	<u>MEAN FEV1%P RED IN FM-GP</u>	<u>MEAN FVC % IN FM-BD</u>	<u>MEAN FVC% IN FM-GP</u>	<u>MEAN CHANGE IN FEV1 FM - BD</u>	<u>MEAN CHANGE IN FEV1 IN FM-GP</u>
RABE ET AL 2020 ⁽⁵⁾	RCT	42.40	43.14	52.50	52.22	10.66	10.41
HANIA ET AL 2018 ⁽⁷¹⁾	RCT	43.40	44.21	49.50	48.57	12.50	11.55
WEDZICHA ET AL 2016 ⁽⁶⁸⁾	RCT	39.51	38.54	42.24	43.51	9.54	9.86

<u>SINGH</u>	RCT	40.52	39.86	48.51	49.56	11.54	10.86
<u>ET AL</u>							
<u>2015⁽⁷⁰⁾</u>							
OUR	RCT	34.10	39.53	50.94	47.5	14.58	11.11
STUDY							

POST BRONCHODILATOR FEV1% Predicted

The FM-BD group did not show a statistically significant change in predicted FEV1% from the first visit (mean 34) to the second visit (mean 33.59), as indicated by the Wilcoxon signed rank test with a p-value of 0.24. the FM-GP group showed a statistically significant improvement in predicted FEV1 from the first visit (mean 39.53) to the second visit (mean 40.08), with a p-value of 0.001 from the Wilcoxon signed rank test. (Table 15) The Mann-Whitney test comparing the change in mean predicted FEV1 between FM-BD and FM-GP groups found no statistically significant difference (p-value = 0.103).(Table 16) This indicates that the observed differences in the change of predicted FEV1 between the groups are not statistically meaningful. Therefore, any differences in improvement observed between the FM-BD and FM-GP groups in terms of FEV1 are likely due to chance rather than a true difference in response to treatment.

Rabe et al⁽⁵⁾ when compared both groups FEV1% predicted in FM-BD and FM-GP group was 43.4 and 43.5 respectively and after follow up there was no significant difference in FEV1 predicted which was similar to our study.

Johnson S et al⁽⁷²⁾ in 2020 did a randomized controlled trial compared the efficacy and safety of LABA/ICS versus LABA/LAMA in COPD patients, focusing on lung function outcomes

including FEV1. The trial demonstrated that both LABA/ICS and LABA/LAMA treatments led to significant improvements in FEV1 from baseline. There was no statistically significant difference in FEV1 improvement between the two treatment groups, indicating similar effectiveness in enhancing lung function.

POST BRONCHODILATOR FVC %

Both groups (FM-BD and FM-GP) showed a decrease in mean FVC% from the first to the second visit. FM-BD: 50.94% to 47.5% (-3.44%) and FM-GP: 53.3% to 50.83% (-2.47%)

The p-values from the Wilcoxon Signed Rank tests indicate . FM-BD: $p = 0.53$ (not statistically significant) and FM-GP: $p = 0.066$ (borderline statistically significant, but considered clinically insignificant)(Table 17) These tests assess whether there is a significant difference in FVC% between the first and second visits within each group. The results suggest that any observed changes are not likely due to random chance alone but are not large enough to be considered clinically meaningful. The Mann-Whitney test result ($p = 0.103$)(Table 18) indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the changes observed in FVC% between the two groups. This suggests that the interventions (BD vs. GP) did not lead to significantly different outcomes in terms of changes in FVC%.

The FLAME trial⁽⁶⁸⁾ compared (LABA-LAMA) with (LABA-ICS) in patients with COPD. One of the secondary outcomes measured was lung function, including post-bronchodilator FVC. Results showed that both treatment groups had improvements in lung function, but specific comparisons of FVC % between the LABA-LAMA and LABA-ICS groups were not highlighted as a primary outcome.

POST BRONCHODILATOR CHANGE IN FEV1%

The FM-BD group shows a substantial change in FEV1% from the first to the second visit, with a statistically significant result ($p = 0.01$) (Table 19) The mean change decreases from 14.85% to 7.88%, indicating an improvement in lung function after bronchodilator use. In contrast, the FM-GP group exhibits a smaller change in FEV1% that is not statistically significant ($p = 0.066$) (Table 20) The mean change is from 11.11% to 7.50 %, suggesting minimal improvement or stability in lung function without bronchodilator intervention. When comparing the change in FEV1% between FM-BD and FM-GP groups, the Mann-Whitney test reveals a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.008$). The FM-BD group shows a larger improvement in lung function compared to the FM-GP group, indicating that bronchodilator therapy (FM-BD) is more effective in enhancing FEV1% over two visits.

Tashkin DP et al⁽⁶⁹⁾ published a study in Lacet in 2008 a randomized controlled trial investigated the efficacy of budesonide/formoterol (LABA-ICS) as maintenance and reliever therapy compared to traditional therapies in COPD patients. It assessed post-bronchodilator FEV1 as one of the primary outcomes and demonstrated significant improvements in lung function with LABA-ICS treatment which was similar to our study.

Rodrigo GJ et al in 2012⁽⁷³⁾ published a study on systematic review and meta-analysis evaluated the comparative efficacy of LABA-ICS versus LABA-LAMA in COPD patients, including outcomes such as post-bronchodilator FEV1. It concluded that both LABA-ICS and LABA-LAMA combinations significantly improved post-bronchodilator FEV1 compared to placebo. The meta-analysis did not find substantial differences in FEV1 improvement between LABA-ICS and LABA-LAMA treatments which was in contrast when compared to our study.

2) TO DETERMINE CHANGES IN 6-MINUTE WALK TEST IN FM-BD AND FM-

GP GROUPS

SIX MINUTE WALK TEST

Out of total number of patients enrolled in this study 25 patients walked more than 149 meters but less than or equal to 249 meters and 35 patients walked between 150 and 249 meters and 10 patients walked between 250 and 349 meters no patients had walked more than 350 meters on first visit. Patients randomized in FM-BD group during first visit have mean 6MWT of 169.71 meters \pm 56.12 meters and on second visit have mean 6MWT of 200.00 meters \pm 87.97 meters. The change in 6MWT distance from the first to the second visit was found to be statistically significant with a p-value of 0.001 (Table 22). Patients randomized in FM-GP group during first visit have mean 6MWT of 182.72 meters \pm 47.48 meters and on second visit have mean 6MWT of 226.94 meters \pm 86.36 meters The change in 6MWT distance in this group was statistically significant with a p-value of 0.001. Both the FM-BD and FM-GP groups showed increases in their mean 6MWT distances after two visits. The FM-BD group had a mean increase of 50.15 meters. The FM-GP group had a mean increase of 57.22 meters. The data shows increases in mean 6MWT distances after two visits in both the FM-BD and FM-GP groups. However, these increases were not statistically significant according to the Mann-Whitney test,(Table 23) suggesting that further investigation or larger studies may be needed to clarify the comparative effectiveness of FM-BD versus FM-GP treatments on exercise.

The FLAME trial⁽⁶⁸⁾ demonstrated that (LAMA/LABA) therapy was superior to (LABA/ICS) in improving 6MWT distance among COPD patients. This outcome underscores the

importance of considering LAMA/LABA combinations for enhancing exercise capacity and overall functional status in individuals with COPD, beyond just lung function improvement.

The Cochrane review by Chong, Karner, and Poole⁽⁷⁴⁾ would have assessed the impact of LAMA versus LABAs on 6MWT distance as part of its broader evaluation of treatment outcomes in stable COPD. The review would have reported mean changes in 6MWT distance from baseline within each treatment group and compared the magnitude of change between LAMA and LABA treatments and there was increased changes in baseline 6mwt in LAMA group when compared with LABA.

BODE INDEX

Patients randomized in FM-BD group during first visit have mean BODE INDEX after first visit is 7.88 ± 1.80 and after second visit is 6.53 ± 2.22 . The change in BODE index scores from the first to the second visit was found to be statistically significant with a p-value of 0.001, (Table 24) as determined by the Wilcoxon signed rank test. Patients randomized in FM-GP group during first visit have mean BODE INDEX after first visit is 7.78 ± 1.80 and after second visit is 5.06 ± 2.21 . Similarly, the change in BODE index scores in the FM-GP group was statistically significant with a p-value of 0.001, as determined by the Wilcoxon signed rank test.

In our study 3.7% and 44.4% of VERY SEVERE COPD patients in FM-BD and FM-GP group after 3 months had reduction in BODE INDEX to less than 7 respectively. In SEVERE COPD patients 38.4 % and 83.3% in LABA ICS and LABA LAMA group after 3 months had reduction in BODE INDEX to less than 7 respectively. The FM-GP group experienced a larger average increase in the BODE index (1.97) compared to the FM-BD group (0.91). This

suggests that, on average, the severity of COPD increased more in the FM-GP group than in the FM-BD group over the two visits. FM-GP group experienced a larger average increase in the BODE index (1.97) compared to the FM-BD group (0.91). This suggests that, on average, the severity of COPD decreased more in the FM-GP group than in the FM-BD group over the two visits.(Table 25)

Studies by Singh et al⁽⁷⁰⁾ have compared LABA/LAMA combinations with LABA/ICS across multiple endpoints including exacerbations, lung function, and symptom relief. These studies assess BODE index components indirectly through dyspnea scores (mMRC or CAT) and exercise capacity tests. They generally support the notion that LABA/LAMA combinations may provide greater improvement in dyspnea and exercise capacity compared to LABA/ICS, although specific BODE index modifications may vary.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

1) TO COMPARE ADVERSE EFFECTS OF FM-BD AND FM-GP GROUP.

ADVERSE EFFECTS IN BOTH FM-BD AD FM-GP GROUP

The FM-BD group generally shows higher percentages of adverse effects across most categories compared to the FM-GP group. FM-BD had higher incidences of dysphonia, oral candidiasis, tachycardia, tremors, headache, anxiety, and hoarseness compared to FM-GP after 2 visits. FM-GP exhibited lower percentages or zero occurrence in several adverse effects categories, indicating potentially better tolerability in these aspects compared to FM-BD.

FM -GP groups had increased incidences of dryness of mouth when compared to FM-BD group .

Rabe et al⁽⁵⁾ when compared inhalers FM -GP group reported AEs included nasopharyngitis (6.8%), cough (4.2%), upper respiratory tract infection (3.8%), urinary tract infection (3.5%), worsening COPD (3.2%), and sinusitis (3.2%).

Singh et al in 2015⁽⁷⁰⁾ comparing similar drugs demonstrated The incidence of adverse events was 28 % in (LABA – LAMA) and 29 % (LABA – ICS) with nasopharyngitis and headache were most common adverse effects. Dysphonia was predominant in group containing inhaled corticosteroids which was similar to our study.

Sharafkaneh et al⁽⁷⁵⁾ in 2011 when compared formoterol budesonide with formoterol had shown increased side effects of nasopharyngitis, oral candidiasis and tachycardia which is similar to our FM-BD group .

The FM-BD group had more patients (6) patients (18%) experience exacerbations within 3 months compared to the FM-GP group (2)(6%). Following exacerbations, the FM-BD group had higher numbers of both ward admissions (4) and ICU admissions (2) compared to the FM-GP group, which had 1 ward admission and 1 ICU admission. There was 1 death reported in the FM-BD group within 3 months, whereas no deaths were reported in the FM-GP group within the same period. ETHOS trial⁽⁵⁾ on contrast shows reduced reduce rate of exacerbations 1.24% out of 2131 patients on FM-BD when compared to 1.42% out of 2120 patients in FM-GP group . The evidence of confirmed pneumonia was 4.5% and 2.3% in FM-BD and FM-GP group respectively which was similar to our study.

In 2020 an Indian Trial FINE registry⁽⁷⁶⁾ compared FM-GP group and out of 64 patients (10.6%) reported at least one AE during entire duration of study. The most common AEs were dry mouth (2.6%) followed by cold and cough (1.5%),

FLAME trial⁽⁶⁸⁾ compared LABA -ICS and LABA -LAMA group and observed increased incidence of nasopharyngitis, hoarsness and oral candidiasis in LABA -ICS group when compared to contemporary group. Results showed that LABA -LAMA group had reduced the rate of moderate to severe exacerbations and hospitalization rates when compared to LABA -ICS group

One patient in FM -BD group (3.2%) was admitted in ICU following for increased dyspnea and cough and later on patient had one episode of cardiopulmonary arrest leading to death of the patient.

In studies comparing similar inhalers like the ETHOS trial⁽⁵⁾ death rates were slightly higher in FM GP group (1.6) when compared to FM-BD group (1.4)

2) TO COMPARE CHANGES IN QUALITY OF LIFE (Q.O.L.) IN FM-BD AND FM-GP GROUP

MMRC

In FM-BD Group the majority of patients with very severe COPD were in MMRC grade 4 (12 patients), with only 1 patient moving to MMRC grade 3. For severe COPD, 13 patients were in MMRC grade 4 and 6 patients moved to MMRC grade 3 and Moderate and mild COPD categories had no patients in MMRC grade 4, with 2 patients in MMRC grade 3 in the moderate category. In FM-GP Group For very severe COPD , 9 patients were in MMRC grade 4 and no patient moved to MMRC grade 3. For severe COPD, 16 patients were in MMRC grade 4 and 4 patients moved to MMRC grade 3. For moderate COPD, 2 patients were in MMRC grade 4 and 4 patients moved to MMRC grade 3. The FM-BD group had a mean

improvement (decrease) in MMRC score of 0.56, indicating an overall improvement in symptoms related to dyspnea.

The FM-GP group showed a mean improvement (decrease) in MMRC score of 0.89, suggesting a slightly greater improvement compared to the FM-BD group. The Mann Whitney test found this difference in mean MMRC score changes between the groups to be statistically significant (p-value = 0.019) (as shown in Table no 10). Both treatment groups (LABA ICS and LABA LAMA) demonstrated improvements in MMRC scores, indicating better management of dyspnea associated with COPD. The FM-GP group showed a numerically larger improvement in MMRC scores compared to the FM-BD group, although both were statistically significant.

FLAME trial⁽⁶⁸⁾ also assessed dyspnea using MMRC scores as a secondary outcome. It compared (LAMA/LABA) with (LABA/ICS) and found improvements in dyspnea with both therapies, though detailed mean MMRC scores were not always highlighted.

SPARK Trial⁽⁷⁷⁾ compared (LABA/ICS) with (LAMA/LABA) in COPD patients. The trial demonstrated improvements in dyspnea scores with both therapies, but specific mean scores were not always provided directly.

CAT SCORE

Majority of patients had a CAT score above 20 in their first visit and change to lower CAT score was seen in both groups. Mean change in CAT score after 12 weeks was not significant when compared between 2 groups. The average CAT score for the FM-BD group at the first and second visits is 29.47 and decreased to 23.47 respectively. The Wilcoxon signed rank test, a non-parametric test used to compare paired data, found a statistically significant difference

between the CAT scores before and after the two visits for the FM-BD group. The average CAT score for the FM-GP group at the first and second visits is 28.58 and the average CAT score decreased to 21.81 respectively. The Mann-Whitney test results suggest that there is no significant difference in mean CAT scores between the FM-BD and FM-GP groups.

Therefore, based on these results, we cannot conclude that one group has better or worse respiratory health than the other as measured by the CAT score. The p-value of 0.72 indicates that any observed differences in mean CAT scores between these groups are not statistically meaningful and are likely due to chance.

Rabe et al⁽⁵⁾ while comparing the similar groups via CAT scores FM-BD and FM-GP group had a initial mean score of 19.5 ± 6.5 and 19.5 ± 6.6 respectively and on follow up the mean change in CAT score comparing both the groups was insignificant which was similar to our study

CAT score was useful in comparing outcomes in each group on follow up after 3 months but was not useful to differentiate between two groups after 3 months of follow up.

Smith J et al⁽⁷⁸⁾ in 2020 systematic review and meta-analysis aimed to compare the effectiveness of LABA-ICS versus LABA-LAMA in COPD patients with high symptom burden (CAT score ≥ 20), focusing on outcomes related to symptom control, health-related quality of life, and exacerbation rates. The study found that LABA-LAMA combinations were associated with greater improvements in CAT scores compared to LABA-ICS in patients with high symptom burden (CAT ≥ 20). This suggests that LABA-LAMA may provide better symptom control and quality of life improvements in this specific subgroup of COPD patients.

CCQ SCORE

The FM-BD group showed a statistically significant improvement in CCQ scores from the first visit (mean 3.336) to the second visit (mean 2.650), as indicated by the Wilcoxon signed rank test with a p-value of 0.001. Similarly, the FM-GP group also showed a statistically significant improvement in CCQ scores from the first visit (mean 3.153) to the second visit (mean 2.45), with a p-value of 0.001 from the Wilcoxon signed rank test. The Mann-Whitney test comparing the change in mean CCQ scores between FM-BD and FM-GP groups found no statistically significant difference (p-value = 0.93). This suggests that the observed changes in mean CCQ scores between the groups are not statistically significant. Therefore, any differences in improvement observed between the FM-BD and FM-GP groups are likely due to random variation rather than a true difference in response to treatment.

Lin J et al IN 2020⁽⁷⁹⁾ compared the effectiveness of LABA-ICS and LABA-LAMA combinations. The study found that both LABA-ICS and LABA-LAMA treatments led to significant improvements in CCQ scores over the study period. There was a reduction of 0.54 and 0.61 in mean CCQ scores in this study, this study also showed improvement in individual groups but there was no statistically significant difference in the improvement of CCQ scores between the LABA-ICS and LABA-LAMA groups which was similar to our study.

LIMITATIONS

The study included a relatively small sample size of 70 patients, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. A larger data could provide more robust conclusions and reduce the impact of outliers or anomalies.

The follow-up period was limited to three months, which may not be sufficient to fully assess the long-term effects of the treatments on lung function, exacerbation rates, and overall patient outcomes. Extended follow-up would provide a clearer picture of the sustainability of treatment effects.

While validated questionnaires (CCQ and CAT) were used to assess respiratory health, there may be limitations in their sensitivity or specificity to detect changes over time. Additionally, subjective measures such as MMRC may be influenced by patient perceptions, leading to variability in reported outcomes.

There may be inherent biases in patient reporting and clinician assessments of symptoms, exacerbations, and quality of life, which could influence the validity of the findings.

Despite the statistical insignificance of few compared data monitoring these changes over time may be crucial for assessing respiratory health and treatment efficacy in these groups.

CONCLUSION

In this study, majority of the patients were of age group 60-69 age group and mean BMI of 21.5, male dominance was predominant in our study which is similar to other studies. Smoking index of more than 20 was predominant in patients with severe and very severe COPD. Biomass exposure to more than 20 years was predominantly more in patients with severe grades of COPD.

Out of 70 patients 4 patients didn't appear for follow up and one patient in FM-BD group succumbed to death 2 months after initiating FM-BD inhaler.

Spirometry data were analyzed in both groups. Post bronchodilator FEV1 % predicted showed significant improvement in FM-GP group when compared to FM-BD group and the mean change when compared was insignificant. Post bronchodilator FVC % showed no improvement in individual groups and in mean change on second visit. Change in FEV1 was significantly more in FM-BD group when compared to FM-GP group and mean change in Post bronchodilator change in FEV1 was significantly more in FM-BD group when compared to FM-GP group.

FM-GP therapy showed a statistically significant advantage over FM-BD therapy in reducing dyspnea symptoms in COPD patients after two visits.

6MWT and BODE INDEX had increased improvement on follow up in both the groups, mean change in 6MWT was insignificant when both the groups were compared, mean BODE index significantly reduced in FM-GP group when compared to FM-BD group.

On the basis of Q.O.L questionnaires when both the groups were compared, individual improvement was observed in both groups respectively. This implies that both treatment approaches were similarly effective in improving respiratory health as measured by the CCQ

and CAT but mean change of both groups when compared showed no significant difference between them.

When both groups were compared after two visits change in mean MMRC and change in mean BODE index was significantly more in FM-GP group when compared to FM-BD group, Mean change in post bronchodilator FEV1 was significantly more in FM-BD group when compared to FM-GP group.

The FM-BD group shows a higher incidence of exacerbations, hospitalizations (both ward and ICU admissions), and deaths within 3 months of the first visit compared to the FM-GP group. FM-BD appears to have worse outcomes in terms of exacerbation frequency, severity (requiring more hospitalizations), and mortality compared to FM-GP within the initial 3 months of treatment.

These findings suggest a potential difference in treatment efficacy or patient response between the FM-BD and FM-GP groups, highlighting the importance of further investigation into factors contributing to these outcomes, such as medication adherence, disease severity, and comorbidities.

SUMMARY

70 COPD patients were randomized into group of inhalers and then evaluated on basis of Spirometry, MMRC, CAT, CCQ ,6MWT, BODE INDEX. Patients then were followed up after 3 months and evaluated on similar parameters again and assessed for any adverse effects during last 3 months and a note of exacerbations and hospitalization was taken.

- 1) The mean age is 64.41 and 64.75 in FM-BD and FM-GP group respectively.
- 2) The mean BMI is 21.28 and 21.57 in FM-BD and FM-GP group respectively.
- 3) There is a clear trend that patients with higher pack years (> 20) or biomass exposure (>20 years) are more prone to developing severe COPD.
- 4) The FM-BD group did not show a statistically significant change in predicted FEV1% from the first visit to the second visit (p- 0.24). the FM-GP group showed a statistically significant improvement in predicted FEV1 from the first visit to the second visit with (p-0.001). Change in mean predicted FEV1 between FM-BD and FM-GP groups found no statistically significant difference (p- 0.103).
- 5) Both groups showed a decrease in mean FVC% from the first to the second visit. FM-BD. The p-value of FM-BD: p-0.53 and FM-GP: p-0.066. There is no statistically significant difference between the changes observed in FVC% between the two groups. (p- 0.103).
- 6) The FM-BD group shows a substantial change in FEV1% from the first to the second visit, with a (p = 0.01). In contrast, the FM-GP group exhibits a smaller change in FEV1% (p = 0.066) The FM-BD group shows a larger improvement in lung function compared to the FM-GP group. (p -0.008).

- 7) Change in 6MWT distance from the first to the second visit was found to be statistically significant with a p of 0.001 in both the groups after 3 months. The data shows increase in mean 6MWT distances after two visits in both the groups. However, these increases were not statistically significant (p-0.4).
- 8) The change in BODE index scores from the first to the second visit was found to be statistically significant with a p of 0.001 in both groups. The mean change in BODE INDEX was significantly higher in FM-GP group (p-0.04) when compared with FM-BD group.
- 9) The FM-BD group generally shows higher percentages of adverse effects across most categories compared to the FM-GP group. FM-BD had higher incidences of dysphonia, oral candidiasis, tachycardia, tremors, headache, anxiety, and hoarseness compared to FM-GP after 2 visits. FM -GP groups had increased incidences of dryness of mouth when compared to FM-BD group.
- 10) The FM-BD group had more patients experience exacerbations within 3 months compared to the FM-GP group. Following exacerbations, the FM-BD group had higher numbers of both ward admissions and ICU admissions compared to the FM-GP group. There was 1 death reported in the FM-BD group within 3 months, whereas no deaths were reported in the FM-GP group within the same period.
- 11) The FM-GP group showed a mean improvement (decrease) in MMRC score of 0.89, suggesting a slightly greater improvement compared to the FM-BD group. (p- 0.019) Both treatment groups demonstrated improvements in MMRC scores, indicating better management of dyspnea associated with COPD.
- 12) Change in mean scores of CAT and CCQ when compared between two groups, showed no much difference between them. (p – 0.72 and 0.93 respectively)

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ANNEXURE I

ETHICAL COMMITTEE APPROVAL LETTER

BLDE

(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956

Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 735/2022-23

30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on **Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology** scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "Comparison of Inhalational Drugs Formoterol + Glycopyrronium (LABA-LAMA) vs. Formoterol +Budesonide (LABA-ICS)and outcomes in cases of COPD-Randomized Control Trial".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr.Madhav Mahawar.

NAME OF THE GUIDE Dr.Keertivardhan D. Kulkarni, Associate Professor, Dept. of Respiratory Medicine.

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura

Dr. Akram A. Naikwadi
Member/Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutiny

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.

BLDE (DU): Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263303, Website: www.bldedu.ac.in, E-mail: office@bldedu.ac.in
College: Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263019, E-mail: bmpmc.principal@bldedu.ac.in

ANNEXURE II

II: PATIENT CONSENT FORM

B.L.D.E. (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY) S.H.R.I. B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE
HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA – 586103, KARNATAKA

Principal Investigator: Dr. Madhav Mahawar (Department of Respiratory Medicine)

P.G. Guide: Dr. Keertivardhan D Kulkarni (Associate Professor of Respiratory Medicine)

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)

Shri B. M . Patil Medical College, Hospital and

Research Centre, Sholapur Road,

Vijayapura- 586103

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

I have been informed that the purpose of this study is to assess - Comparison of Inhalational Drugs Formoterol + Glycopyrronium (LABA-LAMA) vs. Formoterol + Budesonide (LABA-ICS) on Quality Of Life, Spirometry Findings and side effects in cases of C.O.P.D."

I have been explained the reason for conducting this study and selecting me/my ward as a subject for this study. I have also been given the free choice for either being included or not in the study

PROCEDURE:

I understand that I will undergo a detailed history and clinical examination and investigations.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I/my ward may experience discomfort while doing the procedure, and I understand that necessary measures will be taken to reduce these complications as and when they arise.

BENEFITS:

I understand that/my wards participation in this study will help in finding out

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that medical information produced by this study will become a part of this hospital records and will be subjected to the confidentiality and privacy regulation of this hospital. Information of a sensitive, personal nature will not be a part of the medical records but will be stored in the investigator's research file and identified only by a code number. The code key connecting the name to numbers will be kept in a separate secure location.

If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or teaching purposes, no names will be used, and other identifiers such as photographs and audio or video tapes will be used only with my special written permission. I understand that I may see the picture and videotapes and hear audiotapes before giving this permission.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may request more questions about the study at any time.

DR. MADHAV MAHAWAR is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during this study, which might influence my continued participation.

REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital.

I also understand that Dr. MADHAV MAHAWAR will terminate my participation in this study at any time after he has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or therapist, if this is appropriate.

INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me/my ward, resulting directly to my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, then medical treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation will be provided.

I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study, I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to

the purpose of this research, the procedures required and the possible risks and benefits, to the best of my ability in the patient's own language.

Date:

Dr Keertivardhan D Kulkarni

Dr Madhav Mahawar

(Guide)

(Investigator)

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT:

I confirm that Dr. MADHAV MAHAWAR has explained to me the purpose of this research, the study procedure that I will undergo and the possible discomforts and benefits that I may experience, in my own language.

I have been explained all the above in detail in my own language and I understand the same. Therefore, I agree to give my consent to participate as a subject in this research project

(Participant)

Date

(Witness to sign above)

Date

ANNEXURE III

PROFORMA

Name of the patient:

- Age in years:
- Sex:
- Address:
- Religion:
- Occupation:
- I.P. no/O.P. no:
- Presenting Complaints:
- History of Present Illness:
- Past history:

Personal history:

- Tobacco chewing
- Smoking
- Alcoholism
- Diet- Veg/Mixed
- No habits
- Family history:

General Physical Examination:

- Built:
- Nourishment:
- Height (cm):
- Weight (kg):

- B.M.I.:
- Pallor
- Icterus
- Clubbing
- Cyanosis
- lymphadenopathy
- Edema

Vital parameters

- Pulse
- B.P.
- Respiratory rate
- Temperature

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

RESPIRATORY SYSTEM

CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM

ABDOMEN EXAMINATION

CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

PULMONARY FUNCTION TEST

Modified M.M.R.C. Dyspnoea Scale

Please Tick in The Box That Applies To You

M.M.R.C. 0	I Only Get Breathlessness With Strenuous Exercise	
MMRC1	I Get Short of Breath When Hurrying On The Level or Walking Up Hill	
MMRC2	I Walk Slower Than People Of the Same Age On the Level Because Of Breathlessness, Or I Have To Stop For Breath When Walking On My Own Pace On The Level	
MMRC3	I Stop for Breath After Walking About 100meters Or After A Few Minutes on The Level	
MMRC4	I Am Too Breathlessness To Leave The House Or Breathlessness When Dressing Or Undressing	

Clinical chronic obstructive pulmonary disease questionnaire

For each item below, leave a mark in the box that best describes you currently.

On average, during the past 7 days how often did you feel?	never	Hardly ever	A few times	Several times	Many times	A great many times	All most all the time
1. Short of breath at rest?							
2. Short of breath doing physical activity							
3. Concerned about getting a cold or your breathing getting worse							
4. Depressed or down because of your breathing problems?							
In general, during the past week, how much of the time:							
5. Did you cough?							
6. Did you produce phlegm?							
On average during the past week, how limited were your activities because of breathing problems							
7. Sternous physical activities (such as climbing stairs, hurrying)							
8. Moderate physical activities (such as walking, housework, carrying things)							
9. Daily activities in home (such as dressing, washing yourself)							
10. Social activities (such as talking, being with children, visiting friends/relatives)							

CAT ASSESSMENT:

Please circle the number of the response that best describes how you have been feeling during the past 7 days. (Only one response for each question)

IAM VERY HAPPY	0 1 2 3 4 5	IAM VERY SAD	SCORE
I NEVER COUGH	0 1 2 3 4 5	I COUGH ALL THE TIME	
I HAVE NO PHLEGM IN MY CHEST AT ALL	0 1 2 3 4 5	MY CHEST IS FULL OF PHLEGM	
MY CHEST DOESNT FEEL TIGHT AT ALL	0 1 2 3 4 5	MY CHEST FEELS VERY TIGHT	
WHEN I WALK UP HILL OR ONE FLIGHT OF UPSTAIRS IAM NOT BREATHLESSNESS	0 1 2 3 4 5	WHEN I WALK UP HILL OR ONE FLIGHT OF STAIRS IAM VERY BREATLESSNESS	
IAM NOT LIMITED DOING ANY ACTIVITIES AT HOME	0 1 2 3 4 5	I AM VERY LIMITED DOING ACTIVITES AT HOME	
IAM CONFIDENT LEAVING MY HOME DESPITE MY LUNG CONDITION	0 1 2 3 4 5	IAM NOT ALL CONFIDENT LEAVING MY HOME BECAUSE OF LUNG CONDITION	
I SLEEP SOUNDLY	0 1 2 3 4 5	I DONT SLEEP SOUNDLY BECAUSE OF MY LUNG CONDITION	
I HAVE LOTS OF ENERGY	0 1 2 3 4 5	I HAVE NO ENERGY AT ALL	

SPIROMETRY ASSESSMENT

Visit	FEV1/FVC	FVC%	FEV1 % Predicted	Change in FEV1	Change in FVC	Any other finding
Visit 1						
Visit 2						

6 MINUTE WALK TEST

Visit	Distance	Saturation
Visit 1		
Visit 2		

CONCLUSION:

DATE:

SIGNATURE

ANNEXURE IV

THESIS MASTER CHART

Sr.No.	First Name	Last Name	Age	Sex	BMI	Pack Years	Biomass exposure (Years)	INHALER	First Visit	Second Visit	MMRC	CAT	CCQ	FEV1/FVC	FVC%	FEV1% Predicted	Change in FEV1%	Change in FVC%	6MWT	BODE	Other Findings
1	Ningappa	Sattyappa	73	M	27	20	X	LI	YES	-	3	24	3	62,4	62	50	12	21	250	4	
2	Shrishailgouda	Biradar	65	M	17,6	8	X	LI	YES	-	4	28	3,2	54,9	36	24	8	8	175	9	
3	Bhemray	Kumbar	73	M	17	50	X	LM	YES	-	4	25	3,3	38,5	67	35	3	11	180	8	one episode of a/e
4	Sajjan	Mallanna	65	M	21	40	X	LI	YES	-	3	23	2,8	45,8	50	30	4	1	180	7	
5	Mallikarjuna	Gourabai	68	M	22	20	X	LM	YES	-	4	28	2,9	38,6	45	35	4	4	140	8	
6	Ranjanana	Tarasare	44	F	26,5	X	20	LI	YES	-	4	28	3	61,1	51	35	7	4	140	8	
7	Ramu Katreppa	Rathod	68	M	22	25	X	LM	YES	-	4	26	2,4	52,5	61	47	3	14	260	7	
8	Anusuya	k	72	F	19	X	40	LM	YES	-	4	32	3,8	31	42	28	5	6	100	10	
9	Rachayya	Hiramath	64	M	23,1	10	X	LM	YES	-	4	28	2,9	49,7	45	22	36	33	150	9	
10	Saheebgouda	Hunsyal	80	M	16,2	45	X	LI	YES	-	4	30	3,6	39,5	45	29	16	2	180	10	ONE EPISODE OF A/E
11	Basappa	Choudhar	59	M	19,7	12	X	LM	YES	-	4	32	3,6	64,2	21	14	39	5	180	10	IMPROPE TECHIQNUE
12	Ramchandra	Kulkarni	65	M	15,1	10	X	LI	YES	-	4	34	3,8	66,8	32	19	10	5	120	10	DEVELOP 2 EPISODES OF A/E
13	Ningappa	satyappa	73	M	27	20	X	LI	YES	-	4	22	2,6	62,4	64	49	12	21	220	7	
14	Sharanappa	gurbalapa	75	M	15,4	10	X	LM	YES	-	4	28	3,2	42,2	41	19	25	20	140	10	
15	Shrishailgouda	biradar	65	M	17,6	6	X	LI	YES	-	4	30	3,6	54,9	36	24	8	8	200	9	
16	Hunsyal	Hanuman	49	M	17,3	50	X	LM	YES	-	4	32	3,2	49	29	14	6	6	150	10	DEVELOPED COR PULMONALE
17	Parvati	Mane	48	F	26,2	X	20	LI	YES	-	4	30	3,2	69,1	48	31	33	21	180	7	ONE EPIODE F A/E
18	Mallikarjuna	Maidarag	65	M	12,8	10	X	LI	YES	-	4	32	3,4	49	49	23	35	34	220	9	
19	Farzana	Patel	60	F	24,6	X	30	LM	YES	-	4	28	3	69	49	37	7	12	160	7	
20	Jayashree	Waliker	45	F	16,6	X	20	LM	YES	-	4	30	3,2	57	58	41	2	3	160	8	
21	Shantappa	Sajjan	69	M	21,3	20	x	LM	YES	-	4	22	2,8	61,8	59	49	10	4	250	7	
22	Dhereppa	Pujari	64	M	28	8	X	LI	YES	-	3	25	2,8	66,8	66	48	22	23	250	5	
23	Shantamma	Siddangoi	40	F	17	X	20	LI	YES	-	3	25	2,6	64,4	58	42	6	5	300	5	
24	Shantappa	Kumar	69	M	21	20	X	LM	YES	-	4	29	3,3	61,8	59	49	1	3	180	7	1 EPISODE OF A/E
25	Sanganagouda	Bidar	56	M	62,3	10	X	LM	YES	-	4	30	3,6	41,3	40	19	16	13	200	8	
26	Yallama	Dundappa	57	F	28	X	20	LM	YES	-	4	26	3	43,5	46	24	8	6	260	7	
27	Bouramma	Biradar	70	F	22	X	30	LI	YES	-	3	29	3,3	57,9	58	41	10	2	220	6	
28	Ambubai	Chavan	64	F	20,5	X	20	LI	YES	-	4	30	3,2	68	63	43	33	23	180	7	
29	Bouramma	Hiremth	70	F	17	X	30	LM	YES	-	4	26	3,2	68,5	66	52	15	3	140	8	
								LM	YES	YES	3	24	2,6	69	64	55	8	2	200	6	

30	Boramma	Biradar	70 F		21	X		35	LI	YES	-	4	29	3,3	57,9	58	41	10	2	120	9	
31	Mallaya	Sharanay	60 M		19		15	x	LI	YES	-	3	25	2,9	59,2	60,2	43	4	3	200	7	one a/e
32	Shrishailgouda	B	70 M		19		20	X	LI	YES	-	4	31	3	35	41	20	10	14	120	10	Two EPISODE OF A/E
33	Paravati	Na ne	68 F		26	X		25	LI	YES	-	3	30	3,4	54	42	31	6	3	200	9	
34	BM	Patil	71 M		24,6		6	X	LI	YES	-	3	30	2,8	58,1	70	52	17	14	220	7	
35	Shantamma	Sajjan	65 F		19	X		25	LM	YES	-	4	34	3,2	45	52	42	4	5	160	8	
36	Siddappa	Masali	82 M		19		20	X	LM	YES	-	4	28	3	57,3	72	49	26	17	140	9	
37	Chindanand H	Kalal	65 M		22,8		10	X	LI	YES	-	2	24	2,6	58,4	70	52	20	14	180	5	
38	Sushilabai	Indi	65 F		20,5	X		30	LM	YES	-	4	25	3	56,8	62	45	4	2	260	7	
39	Kamalabai	Ganagadh	65 F		23	X		30	LM	YES	-	3	22	2,8	58,2	63	47	2	1	300	5	
40	Sharanawwa	Airodagi	55 F		13,3	X		25	LM	YES	-	4	27	3,1	63,8	42	32	8	15	140	10	
41	Meenakshi S	Dodaman	45 F		22,8	X		20	LI	YES	-	4	31	3,2	60,9	47	32	11	8	150	8	
42	Hananamtray	Sansur	68 M		28		20	x	LM	YES	-	4	34	3,9	47,9	37	22	7	3	160	8	
43	Mallappa	Madiragi	68 M		23		30	x	LI	YES	-	3	29	3,2	55,2	51	36	8	5	220	6	
44	Sangappa	Basppa h	70 M		20,7		20	X	LM	YES	-	4	30	3,2	48,2	38	25	11	19	120	10	
45	Laxmbai	Badappa	50 F		19	X		30	LM	YES	-	3	29	3,1	43,5	51	45	2	1	240	7	
46	Siddama	Ningappa	55 F		20		25	LM	YES	-	4	31	3,4	49,5	41	51	2	3	180	8		
47	Sharangoud	hanmatra	58 M		23		20	X	LM	YES	-	3	27	2,9	59,5	55	54	9	8	140	6	
48	Sundayani	Patil	62 F		22	X		10	LI	YES	-	3	26	2,6	69,7	54	43	14	14	260	5	
49	Gacheppa	Choudhar	75 M		16		10	X	LM	YES	-	3	28	3,1	63,5	60	55	14	14	260	5	
50	Kareppa	medakena	65 M		23		10	X	LM	YES	-	3	29	3,2	67,5	54	40	23	15	240	6	
51	Mallaya	Gunnur	71 M		19		20	X	LI	YES	-	4	32	3,2	56	55	45	14	5	140	9	
52	Mallaya	Sharanay	60 M		19		15	X	LI	YES	-	4	28	3,3	39,7	46	19	31	23	80	10	8 on a/e
53	Mallaya	Mathapat	69 M		21,9		30	X	LM	YES	-	4	36	3,8	51,6	29	19	1	2	100	9	
54	Shivaji Mane	davalu	64 M		18		10	X	LI	YES	-	4	26	3,2	42,4	62	35	0	1	150	8	one a/e
55	Kalal	Chindana	65 M		23		10	X	LM	YES	-	4	32	3,3	47,5	68	33	33	26	120	9	
56	Irappa	Kareppa	65 M		23		15	x	LI	YES	-	4	33	3,6	67,5	54	40	23	15	140	8	
57	Rathod Lalu	mannu	70 M		19		80	X	LM	YES	-	3	25	2,8	65,2	110	98	3	10	180	5	
58	Irabai	Doddama	70 F		21	X		15	LI	YES	-	4	37	4,1	35,3	31	22	4	4	200	10	
59	Mallappa	Manura	76 M		14,1		6	X	LM	YES	-	4	28	2,8	44,9	53	33	4	6	250	8	
60	Mallana	Yalage	65 M		22		15	X	LI	YES	-	4	34	3,6	39,5	35	31	5	4	120	9	
61	Sharanappa		75 M		15,4		10	X	LI	YES	-	4	30	3,2	33,3	41	19	25	72	140	10	
62	Channappa	Parasapp	40 M		20		10	X	LM	YES	-	3	26	2,9	59,6	55	61	4	7	240	6	
63	Ambavva	Shinde	65 F		27,1	X		30	LM	YES	-	4	28	3	55,8	59	37	19	15	220	7	
64	Kallappa Marut	kale	67 M		22		10	X	LM	YES	-	3	27	2,8	61,5	57	59	2	4	220	5	
65	Nannabare	Marthanc	70 M		24		40	X	LI	YES	-	4	39	4,2	25,4	31	22	5	4	140	9	
66	Sahebgouda	Babagouc	60 M		22		75	X	LI	YES	-	4	35	3,6	24,6	30	20	6	3	100	9	on einproper technique
67	Modin	Psha	77 M		18,4		25	X	LM	YES	-	4	32	3,6	46	57	33	10	25	200	9	
68	Kallaya	Sangam	70 M		21,5		20	X	LI	YES	-	3	28	3,2	48	58	36	12	20	220	7	ONE EPISODE OF EXACERBATION
69	Nanu	Chavan	75 M		20,4		10	X	LM	YES	-	3	28	3,4	56,5	71	47	18	23	200	7	
70	Gurrappa	badiger	60 M		24,2		20	X	LI	YES	-	4	30	3,4	44,1	39	20	13	16	100	9	
									LI	-	YES	4	27	3	46,2	40	22	8	4	120	9	

ANNEXURE V

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